

**EVALUATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF NEW
STRATEGY TO ACHIEVE SECURITY AND ENERGY
EFFICIENCY IN WIRELESS NETWORK**

By

Vishal Dattana

A Research Report Submitted for the fulfillment of the

Award of

Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Program in

(WIRELESS NETWORK)

Under Supervision of

Dr. Krishna Prasad K.

Srinivas University, Karnataka, India

**Institute of Computer Science & Information Sciences
Srinivas University**

(A Statutory University under UGC Act, Govt. of India)

Mangaluru- 574 146, Karnataka, India

**EVALUATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF NEW
STRATEGY TO ACHIEVE SECURITY AND ENERGY
EFFICIENCY IN WIRELESS NETWORK**

By

Vishal Dattana

**A Research Report Submitted for the fulfillment of the
award of**

Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Program in

(WIRELESS NETWORK)

Under Supervision of

Dr. Krishna Prasad K.

Srinivas University, Karnataka, India

**Institute of Computer Science & Information
Sciences**

Srinivas University

(A Statutory University under UGC Act, Govt. of India)

Mangaluru- 574 146, Karnataka, India

CERTIFICATES

RESEARCH SUPERVISOR REPORT

This is to certify that the Research Report entitled “Evaluation And Development of New Strategy to Achieve Security and Energy Efficiency in Wireless Network” submitted to Srinivas University, Karnataka, India by Vishal Dattana, for the award of Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate in Wireless Networks is a record of bonafide research work carried out by him under my supervision. The Research Report (consist with the Publications) has reached the standard of regulations for the award and it has not been previously formed for the award of any qualifications or any other similar title to the candidate or any other person.

Krishna -

Prof. (Dr.) Krishna Prasad K,
Professor, Institute of `engineering and
Technology, Srinivas University,
Mangaluru- 574 146, Karnataka, India

DECLARATION

Declaration

I, **Vishal Dattana**, (Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Scholar) hereby declare that the research work presented in this form of Research Report is prepared by me based on my publications (which are never submitted for any qualifications) and all the works have been connected to reach the theme of the topic and its interdisciplinary area. The descriptions and narrations found are purely original and authentic. Moreover, I am responsible for all the contents included in the publications and research report.

Hence, once again I declare that the entire work in this research report is original for the award of *Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Scholar* of **Srinivas University, Karnataka, India**.

Vishal Dattana

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to express my special appreciation and thanks to my PDF supervisor, Prof. Dr. P. Sreeramana Aithal, Vice-Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangalore, for encouraging my research and for allowing me to grow as a research professor. Your advice on both research as well as on my career have been invaluable.

I am wholeheartedly grateful to Sri. CA. A. Raghavendra Rao, President, A. Shama Rao Foundation, Mangalore and also Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangalore, for encouraging me by providing all facilities to carry out this work. I wish to express my sincere thanks to Dr. P. Srinivas Rao, Vice-president, A. Shama Rao Foundation, Mangalore and also Pro-Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangalore, for their support.

I would always be thankful for my family, my mother Smt. Raj Dattana and my father Sri Ved paul Dattana, for their tireless efforts and support in every path I take to achieve my dreams and goals. I would also like to thank my beloved wife, Mrs. Deepika Dattana for keeping me motivated when things were most challenging and supporting me for everything throughout my career.

I am thankful to Prof. Dr. Krishna Prasad K, Professor, Institute of Computer Science and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, City Campus, Mangalore, for mentoring and encouragement.

I take this opportunity to thank ocean of my friends for their assistance during various stages of my research work. I would like to thank God Almighty for giving me the opportunity and guidance to achieve my goal and to be successful.

Vishal Dattana

Paper Publications

List of Paper Publications

The following is the details of Paper Publications in respect of Post-Doctoral Research Fellow Certificate Program in *Wireless Networks* as per the title of the work 'Evaluation and Development of New Strategy to Achieve Security and Energy Efficiency in Wireless Network' in the specified term.

Serial No.	Title of the Paper	Publication Description	Appeared in	Role
1	Optimizing Routing in MANETs with Energy Conservation	<i>International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)</i> , 7(3), 75-87.	Journal	Authored
2	Evaluation and Development of New Strategy to Achieve Security and Energy Efficiency in Wireless Network	Global Scientific Journal, 10(10), 1113-1126.	Journal	Authored
3	Predicting Global Ranking of Universities Across the World Using Machine Learning Regression Technique	International Conference on Teaching and Learning, 156, 1-4.	Journal	Authored
4	Tracking Students' Progress using Big Data Analytics to enhance student's Employability: A Review	International Conference on Teaching and Learning, 156, 1-7.	Journal	Authored

Book Chapter

List of Book Chapter

The following is the details of Book Chapter in respect of Post-Doctoral Research Fellow Certificate Program in *Wireless Networks* as per the title of the work '*Evaluation and Development of New Strategy to Achieve Security and Energy Efficiency in Wireless Network*' in the specified term.

Serial No.	Chapter	Book	Role
1	Blockchain in Healthcare: A Systematic Review and Future Perspectives	Deep Learning for Healthcare Decision Making	Authored

Patent Publication

List of Patent Publication

The following is the details of Patent Publication in respect of Post-Doctoral Research Fellow Certificate Program in *Wireless Networks* as per the title of the work '*Evaluation and Development of New Strategy to Achieve Security and Energy Efficiency in Wireless Network*' in the specified term.

Serial No.	Title of the Patent	Patent Filing Details	Role
1	Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence Based Intelligent Betting System for Sports Prediction	Patent Application No: 2021104722 Date of File: 30th day of March 2022	IP Australia (Australian Patent) Authored & Granted
2	Intelligent System & Method to Protect and Secure Environment of Premises Using IoT Network	Patent Application No: 2021104977 Date of File: 13th day of April 2022	IP Australia (Australian Patent) Authored & Granted

CONTENTS

No. of Contents/ Headings	List of Contents	Page No.
	Title Page	i
	Certificate from Research Centre	iii
	Research Supervisor Certificate	iv
	Declaration	vi
	Acknowledgement	viii
	List of Paper Publications	x
	Book Chapter	xii
	Patent Publication	xiv
	Content Page	xvi
1	Research Proposal	1-15
Paper Publications		
2	Optimizing Routing in MANETs with Energy Conservation	16-28
3	Evaluation and Development of New Strategy to Achieve Security and Energy Efficiency in Wireless Network	29-42
4	Predicting Global Ranking of Universities Across the World Using Machine Learning Regression Technique	43-46
5	Tracking Students' Progress using Big Data Analytics to enhance student's Employability: A Review	47-53
Book Chapter		
6	Blockchain in Healthcare: A Systematic Review and Future Perspectives	54-86
Patent Publication		
7	Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence Based Intelligent Betting System for Sports Prediction	87
8	Intelligent System & Method to Protect and Secure Environment of Premises Using IoT Network	88-90
9	Conclusion	91

Research Proposal

RESEARCH PROPOSAL - Post Doc Research Fellow in Computer Science

NAME OF CANDIDATE : Vishal Dattana

RESEARCH FIELD : Wireless Networks

TOPIC OF RESEARCH : Developing an Intelligent Energy Aware and Secure Routing for Wireless Sensor Networks

ADVISOR: Dr. Krishna Prasad K.

Professor, Institute of Engineering and Technology, Srinivas University, Mangalore

1. Introduction:

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) consist of a number of nodes. In this type of infrastructureless network, nodes communicate without any centralized control or established infrastructure. One node acts as a router. The routing is a challenging task in WSN due to limited bandwidth and transmission range. Some nodes are fix and some moves quickly in this network and change their path quickly. Several small, inexpensive nodes and sensors are deployed in an open, unprotected environment for long periods of time to communication and collection of sensitive data. The nodes in WSN are supposed to self-organise into a network through wireless communication. The capability of self-configuration and wireless communication allows them to be deployed in an ad-hoc fashion in remote and hostile environments without any existing infrastructure. The figure 1 presents a WSN, where a node is forwarding information to the base station via other nodes.

Figure 1: Wireless Sensor Network Architecture

The emerging wireless technologies enable the implementation of sensor networks for a wide range of applications such as for the military, healthcare, surveillances, environmental monitoring, structural health monitoring, automation, and industry control. There are a number of challenges and hurdles in developing communication protocols for WSNs. They are as follows: i) Limited functional capabilities ii) Power factors iii) Environmental factors iv) Transmission channel factors v) Topology management complexity vi) Scalability concerns.

Wireless networks are capable of handling of topology changes and malfunctions in nodes. It is fixed through network reconfiguration. If the node leaves the network and causes link breakages, affected nodes can request new routes to solve the problem. With this action there will be increase the delay. As packets travel in WSN, they experience the problems of Delay, jitter, out-of-order delivery, packet loss or error.

1.2. Characteristics of WSN

The following are the characteristics of wireless sensor networks:

- **Dynamic topology:** Due to the node mobility, the topology of wireless sensor networks changes continuously and unpredictably. The link connectivity among the terminals of the network dynamically varies in an arbitrary manner and is based on the proximity of one node to another node. It is also subjected to frequent disconnection during nodes mobility. WSNs should adapt to the traffic and propagation conditions as well as to the mobility patterns of the mobile network nodes. The mobile nodes in the network dynamically establish routing among themselves as they move about, forming their own network on the fly. Moreover, a user in the WSNs may not only operate within the network, but may require access to a public fixed network
- **Bandwidth:** WSNs have significantly lower bandwidth capacity in comparison with fixed networks. The used air interface has higher bit error rates, which aggravates the expected link quality. Current technologies suitable for the realization of WSNs are IEEE 802.11(b,a) with bandwidth up to 54Mbps and Bluetooth providing bandwidth of 1Mbps. The nature of high bit-error rates of wireless connection might be more profound in WSNs. One end-to-end path can be shared by several sessions. The channel over which the terminals communicate is subjected to noise, fading and interference, and has less bandwidth than a wired network. In some scenarios, the path between any pair of users can traverse multiple wireless links and the links themselves can be heterogeneous.
- **Energy:** All mobile devices will get their energy from batteries, which is a scarce resource. Therefore the energy conservation plays an important role in WSNs. This important resource has to be used very efficiently. One of the most important system design criteria for optimization may be energy conservation.
- **Security:** The nodes and the information in WSNs are exposed to the same threats like in other networks. Additionally to these classical threats, in WSNs there are special threats, e.g. denial of service attacks. Also mobility implies higher security risks than static operations because portable devices may be stolen or their traffic may insecurely cross wireless links. Eavesdropping, spoofing and denial of service attacks should be considered.
- **Autonomous:** No centralized administration entity is required to manage the operation of the different mobile nodes. In WSNs, each mobile terminal is an autonomous node, which may function as both a host and a router. So usually endpoints and switches are indistinguishable in WSNs.
- **Distributed Operation:** Since there is no background network for the central control of the network operations, the control and management of the network is distributed among the terminals. The nodes involved in a WSNs should collaborate among themselves and each node acts as a relay as needed, to implement functions e.g. security and routing.

- **Multi-hop Routing:** Basic types of ad hoc routing algorithms can be single-hop and multihop, based on different link layer attributes and routing protocols. Single-hop WSNs is simple in comparison with multi-hop WSNs in terms of structures and implementation. When delivering data packets from a source to its destination out of the direct wireless transmission range, the packets should be forwarded via one or more intermediate nodes.
- **Light-Weight Terminals:** In most cases, the WSNs nodes are mobile devices with less CPU processing capability, small memory size and low power storage.
- **Infrastructure less and Self Operated:** A wireless sensor network includes several advantages over traditional wireless networks, including: ease of deployment, speed of deployment and decreased dependence on a fixed infrastructure. WSN is attractive because it provides an instant network formation without the presence of fixed base stations and system administrators. Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are quickly gaining popularity as they are potentially low cost solutions to a variety of real-world challenges (**Jabari and Hosseini, 2011**). There are many challenges for building an application using WSN.

1.3. Recent Challenges

The recent challenges in establishing WSNs are illustrated in Figure 2. There are different tracks in WSNs, related with each other. For example, secure routing in WSN cannot go without taking into consideration the Quality of Service (QoS). The advance technologies throw light to seek a solution for better routing algorithm based on Artificial Intelligence Techniques (AI) to handle the challenges of WSN environment.

Figure 2: Recent Challenges in WSN

a) Secure routing in WSN

Routing is the fundamental operation in WSNs that facilitates the establishment of communication links between sensor nodes and the packet delivery. Routing paths are usually established using a single path between the source and destination nodes. Therefore, the availability of data and reliability of communication are necessary (**Akkaya and Younis, 2005**). There are several WSNs routing protocols that try to deliver the data from a sensor to the sink node with minimal cost. Each of these protocols has its own benefits and drawbacks.

The main categories of WSN routing protocols are shown in Figure 3 based on Paradisi study (**Paradisi, 2012**), WSN Routing Protocols can be classified in four main categories based upon:

- The type of communication routes processed within the network for data transmission from the source to sink
- The type of the network structure
- The network operations carried out using these protocols
- The initiator of communications

Figure 3: WSN Routing Protocol Categories

For sensitive environments, it is equally important to safeguard data from malicious activities as well as maintaining the availability and reliability of the network so as to avoid the situation of Denial of Services (DoS). Therefore, securing the routing process is a vital task to ensure the successful operation of the routing tasks. Security aspects in routing protocols have not been given enough attention, since most of the routing protocols in WSNs have not been designed with security requirements in mind. (**Stavrou and Pitsillides, 2010**)

There are many issues in WSN like security, energy efficiency and QoS etc. which needs attention in today's research challenges. There are several security attacks which affect the process of data dissemination. These security attacks spawn at various layers of Internet model which hampers the security of the network. Author's presented a comparative study of some detection and prevention methods of wormhole attack (**Dwivedi et al. 2018**)

There are a few issues that need to be understood while designing security protocols in the routing process:

- Data redundancy specially in Multipath routing
- Routing attacks
- Survivability
- Security not priority in routing protocol design, (mainly optimize for power (CPU / transmissions))
- Exploit redundancy around each sensor
- Achieve desired global behavior with adaptive localized algorithms

There are many types of attacks in WSN. These may be from outside or from inside the network. The link layer is responsible for multiplexing of data stream, data frame detection, medium access and error control. Possible attacks at this layer are collision and exhaustion. The attackers use different types of devices to attack WSNs. These devices have different power, radio antenna and other capabilities. There are two common categories of them, including mote-class attackers and laptop-class attackers. The explanation of these categories is beyond the scope of present study.

b) Energy Consumption and other factors

One of the basic challenges in design of WSN is maximizing the lifetime of the nodes and sensors, because of placement in remote places. To extend the battery lifetime, energy management is very important and a critical aspect, for this different techniques are needed. Stability of the WSN is also a big challenge for smooth functioning of the network. The WSN has to work with limited resources, unreliable communication channel, delay due to limited bandwidth, transmission loss, transmission errors and noise.

2. Literature Review

A number of state-of-the-art reviews exist today in WSNs, covering from broad to specific areas of interest. However, a comprehensive review on secure routing issues in WSNs appears to be missing. Also in developing country like India, economical networking is very important.

However, the need for secure routing in WSN applications has lead researchers to design secure routing protocols. Currently, some efforts for reviewing WSN secure routing protocols can be found in the literature. These reviews neither focus on all secure routing issues nor cover the method by which one can apply these issues of existing WSN secure routing protocols.

An ad-hoc network is a self-configuring infrastructure-less network of mobile devices connected by wireless. There are new challenges for routing protocols in ad-hoc network. In this paper author focus attention on current protocols which provides connectivity in ad-hoc networks, such as routing protocols. In particular, in ad-hoc network, any node may compromise the routing protocol functionality by disrupting the route discovery process. This paper discusses about table-driven routing protocols belonging to each category (**Hemagowri J. et al., 2004**).

Akkaya and Younis (2005) presented advances in wireless sensor networks where energy awareness is an essential consideration that lead to several new protocols exclusively designed for sensor networks. The author's had studied on recent routing protocols for sensor networks and presented a classification for the various approaches pursued.

Nack (2005) laid stress on WSNs which are infrastructures containing sensing, computing and communication elements. They aimed to give its controllers the ability to measure, collect and react to occurrences in the monitored environment. The limitation of this study has been less focus on security aspects and higher reliability for these systems.

Barbancho et al. (2007) proposed a new AI-based routing algorithm for WSN. This algorithm is called Sensor Intelligence Router (SIR) which has the novelty of being based on the introduction of neural networks in every sensor node. The author's concluded that SIR is the

best suited algorithm among all AI techniques. As it is the Self Organizing Map (SOM) due to the processing constraints. It has been observed that SIR protocol gave better results compared to other algorithms. But it is suitable only for flat-architecture of the WSN.

Boukerche et al. (2008) explored that in the military and emergency preparedness class of applications, WSNs have an important role. One of the main challenges in this kind of application is security. The author's showed how current localization systems are vulnerable to these security attacks and how existing techniques could be used to prevent or impede these attacks in WSNs.

Sen (2009) discussed that WSNs have attracted a lot of interest in the research community due their wide range of applications. These networks were vulnerable to numerous security threats that could adversely affect their proper functioning due to distributed nature of these networks and their deployment in remote areas.

Stavrou and Pitsillides (2010) have reviewed the WSN multipath routing protocols. But they have not taken into consideration the attacks that can greatly influence the network. Some researchers have made attempt to use AI algorithms in routing process. Each of them focuses in a specific problem such as power consuming. There is no attempt to use these algorithms in order to achieve highly secure and fast routing algorithm.

Çelik et al. (2010) deals with problems such as complexity, scalability, adaptability, survivability and battery life in wireless systems. Author's discussed on swarm intelligence based routing protocols for wireless sensor networks. When the previous work was investigated in the field of research, it was seen that routing protocols for WSNs were implementations from wired networks.

Saleema et al. (2011) have reviewed the swarm intelligent based routing protocols in WSN and suggested a new framework. The proposed framework consists of five top level modules and some additional sub-modules. The top level modules are: (i) mobile agent generation and management, (ii) Routing Information Database (RID), (iii) agent structure, (iv) agent communications and (v) packet forwarding.

Shivahare et al. (2012) conducted a survey of protocol properties of various MANET routing algorithms and analyzed them. The routing algorithms considered are classified into two categories: proactive (table driven) and reactive (on demand). The algorithms considered are Destination Sequenced Distance Vector (DSDV), Dynamic Source Routing (DSR), and Ad hoc On Demand Distance Vector (AODV). The comparison among three routing protocols are based on the various protocol property parameters such as Route Discovery, Network Overhead, Periodic Broadcast, Node overheads etc.

S. Singh, and C.S. Raghavendra (2012) in their research paper entitled 'PAMAS—Power Aware Multi-Access Protocol with Signalling for Ad Hoc Networks' proposed a new multiaccess protocol for ad hoc radio networks. The protocol is based on the original MACA protocol with the addition of a separate signalling channel. The unique feature of protocol is that it conserves battery power at nodes by intelligently powering off nodes that are not actively transmitting or receiving packets.

Gaur (2013) contributed in the research work and their implementation is carried out using network simulator. This simulator was provided and visualized using the NETANIM tool. In this paper, introduction to an efficient and effective routing algorithm is briefed using the concept of genetic algorithm. The results were evaluated after performance analysis, author found that genetic algorithm based routing protocol simulated better performance than traditional routing.

Alsheikh et al. (2014) focused on WSNs that are different from traditional network in multiple aspects. In previous studies, many design challenges in WSNs have been resolved using several machine learning methods. The author's concluded that adopting machine learning algorithms in WSNs has to consider the limited resources of the network.

Bala (2015) laid stress on WSNs which was having the sensing, computational and transmission power that consisted of small or large number of sensing nodes whenever any device comes within the frequency range it could get access to the transmitting data and might affect the transmission. Author has discussed all the modes of AODV (simple mode, frequency hopping and malicious node) along with their working. In this work, AODV in a WSN was simulated with different operation modes.

Kumar and Kumar (2015) proposed that to create a WSN which is more energy efficient, swarm intelligence technique has to be applied. In many existing clustering techniques an Artificial Bee Colony(ABC) algorithm is utilized to collect information from the field periodically. Nevertheless, in the event based applications, an Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) is a good solution to enhance the network lifespan. The author's have proposed a new hybrid ABC-ACO algorithm to solve a Nondeterministic Polynomial (NP) hard and finite problem of WSNs. The simulation results showed that the ABC-ACO algorithm enhanced the stability period by 60 percent.

Rahayu et al. (2015) argued that the role of a secure routing would be rendered useless if the data aggregation scheme built on it, is not secure. In an attempt to provide a solution to this problem, author's proposed a secure routing protocol that considered secure data aggregation. The proposed protocol spends a lot of its energy-efficient features for facilitating security compared to the other protocols under evaluation.

Sharma et al. (2015) proposed a method for cluster head selection that used the concept of maximum energy left with the nodes to become cluster head i.e. a node was chosen cluster head when the amount of energy left with the node was maximum amongst all the neighboring nodes to keep the network alive.

Anasane and Satao (2016) discussed that Multimedia Sensor Networks is also the trending topic of discussion due to its application in various fields. Author's presented an effective analysis of various protocols and schemes related to multipath routing in WSNs. The author's suggested that future research can be conducted on reducing the transmission delay in the network, increasing the efficiency and thus the throughput of the system.

Gui et al. (2016) discussed the general principle of Swarm Intelligence(SI) and surveyed the research efforts on these SI based protocols and secondly presented the properties of termite

colony optimization and fission-fusion social structure based spider monkey optimization based clustering in WSNs for discovering the optimal route path and preventing residual nodes.

Warriera and Kumar (2016) focused on technological advancements in wireless communication that have paved way to the development of tiny low-cost, low-power and multifunctional sensor nodes in WSNs. Since radio transmission and reception consumes large amount of energy, power is considered to be an important factor to be investigated for. An energy harvesting WSNs make use of nodes that are able to harvest energy from the environment.

Govindasamy and Punniakody (2017) proposed that the performance metrics such as throughput, average end-to-end delay and energy consumption for AODV, OLSR and ZRP routing protocols of WSN with wormhole attacks were evaluated in static and dynamic WSN. Hence, a proposal was made in order to prevent the security threats in resource constrained WSNs by designing a secure routing protocol or energy efficient intrusion detection system.

Chen et al. (2017) explored that the location information is one of the most crucial pieces of information required to achieve intelligent and context-aware Internet of Things (IoT) systems. Author's surveyed solutions for improving the robustness, security and privacy of locationbased services in IoT systems using cryptographic techniques.

Nayyar and Singh (2017) focused on the main central point of attraction which is the concept of SI based techniques integration in WSNs. The main objective of this research paper is to simulate as well as compare the performance of various existing routing protocols like AODV, DSDV and DSR routing protocols with ACO Based Routing Protocol in terms of End to End Delay, Packet Delivery Rate, Routing Overhead, Throughput and Energy Efficiency.

Mobile ad hoc network is an infrastructure-less network. Each node consists of a router and a host, usually on the same computer. If these nodes are directly in contact with each other they can communicate directly, otherwise the nodes have to communicate by using the intermediate node. These protocols have limited bandwidth, limited power supply, mobility and routing overhead. A number of routing protocols have been designed to overcome these issues. Author's presented a review for hybrid routing protocols Zone Routing Protocol (ZRP), Hybrid Cluster Routing (HCR) and AntHocNet (**Kaur and Singh, 2017**).

WSN is a collection of various sensor nodes. There are many issues in WSN like security, energy efficiency and QoS etc. which needs attention in today's research challenges. There are several security attacks which affect the process of data dissemination. These security attacks spawn at various layers of Internet model which hampers the security of the network. Author's presented a comparative study of some detection and prevention methods of wormhole attack. The various wormhole attack models and different modes of wormhole attack are also discussed in the paper (**Dwivedi et al., 2018**).

Feng Mao et al. (2019) reviews of the development of low-cost sensor networks(LCSNs) over the last 15 years, highlighting trends and future opportunities for a diverse range of environmental applications. Author's findings highlight three distinct opportunities for future research to unleash the full potential of LCSNs: improvement of links between data collection and downstream activities; the potential to broaden the scope of application systems and fields;

and to better integrate stakeholder engagement and sustainable operation to enable longer and greater societal impacts.

M. Anand & T. Sasikala, discussed Efficient energy optimization in mobile ad hoc network (MANET) using better-quality AODV protocol”, Springer, Cluster Computing, Volume 22, pp. 12681–12687, 2019.

Jin Wang et al. (2019) in their paper discussed the energy efficient routing schema combined with clustering and sink mobility technology. The whole sensor field was divided into sectors and each sector elects a Cluster Head (CH) by calculating its members’ weight. The member nodes calculate energy consumption of different routing paths to choose the optimal scenario. The CHs are connected into a chain using the greedy algorithm for inter-cluster communication. Additionally, author’s explored the influence of different network parameters on the performance of the network and further enhanced its performance.

Underwater Wireless Sensor Networks (UWSNs) contain several components such as vehicles and sensors that are deployed in a specific acoustic area to perform collaborative monitoring and data collection tasks. The UWSNs face issues and challenges regarding limited bandwidth, high propagation delay, 3D topology, media access control, routing, resource utilization, and power constraints. The author’s compared available methodologies and discussed their problems and constraints to highlight new directions of research for further improvements in UWSN (**Khalid et al., 2019**).

WSNs are being used widely in different fields like environment, disaster relief, target tracking and several other applications like the SCADA system for the high voltage of electricity. In many applications, node localization is very important in which the system needed to know the exact location of the event. In this paper author’s addressed the main ideas and techniques published in recent years and highlighted the error performance analysis between the algorithms stated static 3D localization (**Kevin et al., 2019**).

Zhang and Yang (2020) High-speed mobility and heavy-load traffic in (MANET) may result in frequent topology changes and packet loss. To guarantee packet delivery, a novel stable backup routing (SBR) scheme is put forward, which consists of the establishment of backup routes and route maintenance. To repair broken links effectively and reasonably, qualified backup routes are classified into three categories with different priorities, based on which the relevant nodes decide how to reconstruct the forwarding path. Extensive simulations demonstrate that our proposed method outperforms other comparable backup routing mechanisms in terms of packet delivery ratio, average delay and control overhead.

3. Research Gap and Problem formulation

Many research activities have been ongoing the aim to secure the routing process in WSN. Each of these tries to solve and fix the problem. This manuscript gives an overview of the current state of the solutions on key issues such as secure routing. WSN introduces security problems, threats, risks and other type of attacks like internal and external attacks. The first challenges of security in sensor network lies in the conflicting interest between minimizing resource consumption and maximizing security.

Secondly the capabilities and constraints of sensor node hardware will influence the type of security mechanisms that can be hosted on a sensor node platform.

The attacks on a WSN can target any node. The damages can include leaking secret information, interfering messages and impersonating nodes. As a result there is a need to present an intelligence-based routing protocol for WSN that integrates security and reduces communication overhead by removing data redundancy from the network. The research methodology should be adopted to provide security to the network without spending additional energy resources, particularly when dealing with high levels of redundancy.

4. Objectives of the Study

- Studying various factors for making network deployment economical using latest infrastructure and techniques.
- Developing an intelligent WSN network using self-healing methods to take care of failures.
- To propose an energy efficient routing strategy for saving energy consumption. • Development of security algorithm to achieve security targets.
- Comparing results with existing schemes and evaluating performance of new framework using simulator.

5. Research Methodology

Methodology will be the Review of Previous Study (Literature Review) and improving the already existing security algorithms and developing new algorithms to increase hardness of security and improve performance. The proposed framework as shown in figure 3 determines the main phases that will be followed in order to create a new AI-based routing protocol for WSN. There are three main phases: Design phase, testing phase, and performance measurement phase. Each of these steps contains a set of tasks. Each task can be understood from its name as shown in figure 4.

The network will be established with the help of simulator NS2. The intrusion of malicious nodes will be detected and metrics would be measured to check the efficiency of the network like PDF, Delay, Throughput, Jitter, Load. The graphical notations will be used. The comparison with the existing protocols will be done, these are explained in next section.

5.1. Performance Metrics

Performance Metrics encompasses the quality of service to the end-user in terms of generic parameters. The perceived quality of service can be quantitatively measured in terms of several parameters. In this manuscript, throughput, average delay, average jitter, packet loss, end-to-end delay, Packet delivery fraction and energy were considered.

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Figure 4: The Proposed Framework

Throughput: Throughput (TP) is a measure of the data rate i.e. bits per second (bps) generated by the application. The equation (i) shows the calculation for throughput TP, where PacketSize is the packet size of the *i*th packet reaching the destination; PacketStart is the time when the first packet left the source and; PacketArrival is the time when the last packet arrived.

$$TP = \text{PacketSize}/(\text{PacketArrival} - \text{PacketStart}) \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

The track of each data packet can be traced from the trace file using packet ID. The time a packet is sent, the time when the packet was received and the packet size is stored for all packets

that reached the destination. To calculate TP, the size of each packet was added. This gives the total data transferred. The total time is calculated as the difference between the time the first packet started and the time the last packet reached the destination. Thus TP is equal to the total data transferred divided by the total time it took for the transfer.

Average Delay: The latency (or delay) would be time taken by the packets to transverse from the source to the destination. The delay can be further categorized into: source-processing delay, propagation delay, network delay and destination processing delay. The equation (ii) shows the calculation for Average Delay, where PacketArrival is the time when packet i reaches the destination and PacketStart is the time when packet i" leaves the source. n is the total number of packets.

$$\text{Average delay} = (\text{Packet Arrival} - \text{Packet Start}) / n \quad \text{Average Jitter} \dots \dots \dots (ii)$$

Delay variation is the variation in the delay introduced by the components along the communication path. It is the variation in the time between packets arriving. Jitter is commonly used as an indicator of consistency and stability of a network. Measuring jitter is critical element to determining the performance of network and the QoS the network offers.

$$\text{Average Jitter} = ((\text{Packet Arrival} + 1) - (\text{Packet Start} + 1)) - ((\text{Packet Arrival}) - (\text{Packet Start})) / n - 1 \dots (iii)$$

Packet Loss: The packet loss affects the perceived quality of the application. Several causes of packet loss or corruption would be bit errors in an erroneous wireless network or insufficient buffers due to network congestion when the channel becomes overloaded. The equation (iv) defines the packet loss.

$$\text{Packet Loss} = ((\text{Lost Packet Size} / \text{Packet Size}) * 100) \quad \text{Packet Delivery Fraction} \dots (iv)$$

The ratio of the data packets delivered to the destinations to those generated by the CBR sources is known as packet delivery fraction.

End-to-End Delay: The network delay is the total latency experienced by a packet to traverse the network from the source to the destination. At the network layer, the end-to-end packet latency is the sum of processing delay, packet, transmission delay, queuing delay and propagation delay. The end-to- end delay of a path is the sum of the node delay at each node plus the link delay at each link on the path.

Energy: The total energy consumed for packets transmitted and packet receiving during the simulation.

5.2. Tool for Simulation

The network simulator 2 (NS-2) is a tool for the simulation of packet-switched networks. It provides substantial support for simulation of Routing and MAC protocols over fixed and wireless networks. The simulator core is written in c plus plus and has object oriented design features. It has an Object Tool Command Language (OTel) interpreter shell as the user interface and allows input models written as Tool Command Language (TCL) scripts to be executed. It is freely distributed and all the source code is available. The network topology and traffic agents are specified in the TCL file. When NS-2 is run, the resulting data could be obtained in a trace

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

file format. The trace file contains time stamp and information about each packet that is sent, received or dropped. It also has information about the packet size, type of packet etc. A base station and a subscriber station can be set up as a node in NS-2. As the number of nodes in the simulation increase, the packets that are sent and received increases. This makes the trace file very large.

6. Work Plan

Work Plan	1 st Year		2 nd Year		3 rd Year	
	1-6 months	6-12 months	1-6 months	6-12 months	1-6 months	6-12 months
Course Work	√					
Literature Survey		√	√	√		
Objectives					√	√
Manuscript Writing					√	√

7. References

- Akkaya K. and Younis M. (2005), "A survey of routing protocols in wireless sensor networks and Ad hoc Network", Elsevier Journal, 3(3), 325-349.
- Alsheikh, M. A., Lin, S., Niyato, D. (2014), Tan, H. "Machine Learning in Wireless Sensor Networks: Algorithms, Strategies, and Applications", IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials, ISSN: 1553-877X,16(4),1996 – 2018.
- Anasane, A. A., Satao, R. A. (2016), "A Survey on Various Multipath Routing Protocols in Wireless Sensor Networks", In Proceeding of 7th International Conference on Communication, Computing and Virtualization, Procedia Computer Science, ISSN: 1877-0509, 79, 610 – 615.
- Bala, R., Singh, Y. (2015), "Secure Routing in Wireless Sensor Network", International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing, 4(5), 966-973.
- Barbancho J., Leon C., Molina F. and Barbancho A. (2007), "Using Artificial Intelligence in Routing Schemes for Wireless Networks", Computer Communications, 30, 14-15.
- Boukerche A., Oliveira H., Nakamura E., and Loureiro A. (2008), "Secure Localization Algorithms for Wireless Sensor Networks", University of Ottawa, Ottawa, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/3200284>, IEEE Communications Magazine · May 2008,96-101.
- Chen, L., Thombre, S., Järvinen, K., Lohan, E. S., Alén-Savikko, A., Leppäkoski, H., Bhuiyan, M. Z. H., Bu-Pasha, S., Ferrara, G. N., Honkala, S., Lindqvist, J., Ruotsalainen, L., Korpisaari, P., Kuusniemi, H. (2017), "Robustness Security and Privacy in Location-Based Services for Future IoT: A Survey", Access IEEE Special Section on Security and Privacy in Applications and Services for Future Internet of Things, ISSN: 2169-3536,5, 8956-8977.
- Çelik, F., Zengin, A., Tuncel, S. (2010), "A Survey on Swarm Intelligence Based Routing Protocols in Wireless Sensor Networks", International Journal of the Physical Sciences, ISSN: 1992-1950, 5(14), 2118-2126.
- David A. Carts (2001), "A Review of the Diffie-Hellman Algorithm and its Use in Secure Internet Protocols", SANS Institute InfoSec Reading Room. Desai S., Butani S. and Valiveti S. (2012), "Analyzing the Impact of Standard Encryption Approaches for Data Aggregation in

a Wireless Sensor Network", International Journal of Computer Science and Telecommunications, 3(6),55-59.

Dwivedi R K, Sharma P and Kumar R (2018), "Detection and Prevention Analysis of Wormhole Attack in Wireless Sensor Network" IEEE , 978-1-5386-1719- 9/18/\$31.00, 8th International Conference on Cloud Computing, Data Science & Engineering (Confluence),727-732.

Esslinger, B (2007), "CrypTool, Version 1.4.10" Deutsche Bank AG, Frankfurt/Main, University of Siegen and Darmstadt, July, www.cryptool.org

Esslinger, B. (2016), "CrypTool: An Open-Source E-Learning Project for Cryptography and Cryptanalysis", 25th Crypto Day in Walldorf, Germany.

Gaur, P. (2013), "An Efficient Routing Implementation Using Genetic Algorithm", International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing (IJCSMC), ISSN: 2320–088X, 2(7), 250 – 257.

Gui, T., Ma, C., Wang, F., Wilkins, D. E. (2016), "Survey on Swarm Intelligence Based Routing Protocols for Wireless Sensor Networks: An Extensive Study", IEEE International Conference on Industrial Technology, ISBN: 978-1-4673-8075-1, 1944-1949.

Govindasamy J., Punniakody, S,(2017), "A Comparative Study of Reactive, Proactive and Hybrid Routing Protocol in Wireless Sensor Network Under Wormhole Attack", Journal of Electrical Systems and Information Technology, ISSN: 2314-7172, ELSEVIER Corrected Proof, 1-10, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/doi:10.1016/j.jesit.2017.02.002>.

Hemagowri J., Baranikumari C., and Brindha B., (2004) "A Study on Proactive Routing Protocol in Ad-hoc network," Int. J. Mod. Eng. Res., National Conference on Architecture, Software systems and Green computing (NCASG), 4–7.

Indu and Dixit Sunita, "Wireless Sensor Networks: Issues & Challenges", International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing, 3(6), 681 – 685

abari Lotf J. and Hossein Hosseini Nazhad Ghazan S., (2011), "Overview on Wireless Sensor Networks ", Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research, ISSN 2090- 4304, 1(12), 28112816.

Kadi, M., Alkhatat, I, (2015), "The Effect of Location Errors on Location Based Routing Protocols in Wireless Sensor Networks", Egyptian Informatics Journal, ISSN: 1110- 8665, 16(1), 113-119, DOI: 10.1016/j.eij.2015.02.001.

Karthik S., Dr Kumar Ashok A. (2015), "Challenges of Wireless Sensor Networks and Issues associated with Time Synchronization", Special Issue Published in Int. Jnl. Of Advanced Networking and Applications(IJANA), Proceedings of the UGC Sponsored National Conference on Advanced Networking and Applications ,19- 23.

Kaur, K(2012), "Performance Evaluation of Ciphers Using CRYPTOOL 2.0", International Journal of Computer & Technology, ISSN: 2277-3061, Vol. 3(1), 39-43.

Kaur H, Singh J (2017), "Analysis of Hybrid Routing Protocols ZRP, HCR and ANTHOCNET: A Review", International Journals of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering ISSN: 2277-128X , DOI: 10.23956/ijarcsse/V7I6/0289 1(6), 642-647.

Kevin, P., Viely, D. and Samarakoon, U.T. (2019), "Performance Analysis of Wireless Sensor

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Network Localization Algorithms” , International Journal of Computer Networks and Applications (IJCNA), ISSN: 2395-0455 ,Vol. 6(6), 92-99.

Kumar R., Kumar, D., (2015), "Hybrid Swarm Intelligence Energy Efficient Clustered Routing Algorithm for Wireless Sensor Networks", Journal of Sensors, Hindawi Publishing Corporation, ISSN: 1687-725X, Vol. 2016,1-19.

Kumar A, Kamboj M. (2017), “Intelligent and Economical Secure Routing Algorithm for Wireless Sensor Network”, International Journal of Innovations & Advancement in Computer Science, ISSN 2347 – 8616, 6(8), 67-73.

Mahmood K, A, Shah, P.A., Iqbal, K, Gillani, S, Ahmad, W and Nam, Y, ”Underwater Wireless Sensor Networks: A Review of Recent Issues and Challenges” (2019), Volume 2019, Article ID 6470359, 20 pages, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/6470359>.

Mao, F, Khamis, K, Krause, S, Clark, J and Hannah, D.A, (2019), “Low-Cost Environmental Sensor Networks: Recent Advances and Future Directions”. published: 11 September 2019 , doi: 10.3389/feart.2019.00221.

Menezes A.,Van Oorschot P., and Vanstone S. (1997), "Handbook of Applied Cryptography", CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, <http://kickme.to/tiger/>.

Nack, F. (2005), "An Overview on Wireless Sensor Networks", Journal of Computer Research and Development, 42(1), 1-8.

Nayyar, A., Singh, R. (2017), "Simulation and Performance Comparison of Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) Routing Protocol with AODV, DSDV, DSR Routing Protocols of Wireless Sensor Networks using NS-2 Simulator", American Journal of Intelligent Systems, ISSN: 2165-8994 (online), 7(1), 19-30.

Paradisi A., (2012), "A pedagogical platform for studying routing algorithms for Wireless Sensor Networks", Master thesis in computer sciences -Vrije university - Brussels

Rodrigo R., Lopez J. (2009), "Integrating wireless sensor networks and the internet: a security analysis", Internet Research, <https://www.nics.uma.es/publications>, (19), 246-259.

Rahayu, T. M., Lee, S., Lee, H. (2015), "A Secure Routing Protocol for Wireless Sensor Networks Considering Secure Data Aggregation", Sensors, ISSN: 1424-8220, 15(7), 1512715158.

Saleema M, Di Caro G. and Farooq M. (2011), "Swarm intelligence based routing protocol for wireless sensor networks: Survey and future directions", Information Sciences, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2010.07.005>, 181(20), 1-28.

Sharma, S., Sethi, D. Bhattacharya, P. P.(2015), "Artificial Neural Network Based Cluster Head Selection in Wireless Sensor Network", International Journal of Computer Applications, ISSN: 0975–8887, 4 (119), 34-41.

Shivhare B. D., C. Wahi, and S. Shalini, (2012), “Comparison Of Proactive And Reactive Routing Protocols In Mobile Adhoc Network Using Routing Protocol Property ;,” Int. J. Emerg. Technol. Adv. Eng., 2(3), 356–359.

Sen, J. (2009), "A Survey on Wireless Sensor Network Security", International Journal of Communication Networks and Information Security (IJCNIS), 1(2),55-78.

Stavrou E. and Pitsillides A. (2010), "A Survey on Secure Multipath Routing Protocols in WSNs",Computer Networks Journal, 54(13), 2215-2238.

M. Anand & T. Sasikala, (2019) “Efficient energy optimization in mobile ad hoc network

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

(MANET) using better-quality AODV protocol”, Springer, Cluster Computing, Volume 22, pp. 12681–12687, 2019.

Walters J., Liang Z., Shi W., and Chaudhary V. (2006), "Wireless sensor network security: a survey", in Xiao, Y. (Eds), Security in Distributed, Grid, and Pervasive Computing, Chapter 17, CRC Press, London.

Wang, J., Gao, Y., Liu, W., Kumar, K.S., and Kim, H., (2019), “Energy Efficient Routing Algorithm with Mobile Sink Support for Wireless Sensor Networks. Published: 27 March 2019, doi:10.3390/s19071494, www.mdpi.com/journal/sensors.

Warriera, M. M., Kumar, A. (2016), "An Energy Efficient Approach for Routing in Wireless Sensor Networks", In Proceedings of 1st Global Colloquium in Recent Advancement and Effectual Researches in Engineering, Science and Technology (RAEREST 2016), Procedia Technology, 25, 520 – 527.

Zhang F. and Yang G. (2020), “A Stable Backup Routing Protocol for Wireless Ad Hoc Networks” ; doi:10.3390/s20236743, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/s20236743>

Optimizing Routing in MANETs with Energy Conservation

Vishal Dattana ¹ & Krishna Prasad K. ²

¹ Post Doctoral Research Fellow, Institute of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India,

Orchid ID: 0000-0002-0661-1174; Email: vishaldattana@gmail.com

² Professor, Institute of Engineering and Technology, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India,

Orchid ID: 0000-0001-5282-9038; Email: krishnaprasadkcci@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Subject Area: Computer Science.

Type of the Paper: Review based Analysis.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [C/O/P/E](#) guidance.

Indexed In: OpenAIRE.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8264993>

Google Scholar Citation: [IJAEML](#)

How to Cite this Paper:

Dattana, V., & Krishna Prasad, K. (2023). Optimizing Routing in MANETs with Energy Conservation. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 7(3), 75-87. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8264993>

International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

Crossref DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJAEML.2581.7000.0189>

Received on: 10/05/2023

Published on: 28/08/2023

© With Authors.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution-Non-Commercial 4.0 International License](#) subject to proper citation to the publication source of the work.

Disclaimer: The scholarly papers as reviewed and published by Srinivas Publications (S.P.), India are the views and opinions of their respective authors and are not the views or opinions of the S.P. The S.P. disclaims of any harm or loss caused due to the published content to any party.

Optimizing Routing in MANETs with Energy Conservation

Vishal Dattana¹ & Krishna Prasad K.²

¹ Post Doctoral Research Fellow, Institute of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India,

Orchid ID: 0000-0002-0661-1174; Email: vishaldattana@gmail.com

² Professor, Institute of Engineering and Technology, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India,

Orchid ID: 0000-0001-5282-9038; Email: krishnaprasadkcci@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

ABSTRACT

Context: In Wireless Networks, MANETs can dynamically create a network without relying on a central hub or infrastructure. These features will be helpful for scenarios such as disaster relief or military operations. However, the absence of a central authority presents challenges concerning security and routing, affecting the network's stability and capabilities.

Approach: A proposed scheme incorporates the consideration of the power factor when selecting routes to handle the challenges efficiently. These are integrated with the widely used AODV routing protocol and simulated using the NS-2 simulator. We evaluate the simulated results to determine the impact of the proposed scheme on the network.

Findings: The simulation outcomes demonstrate that the suggested approach significantly improves network performance concerning power consumption and stability. Including the power factor in route selection positively influences the network's capacity to maintain efficient communication and reduce the energy consumed.

Type of paper: Review based Analysis.

Keywords: Power Factor, MANETs, AODV, ENERGY.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Wireless networks are rapidly advancing, enabling users to access information and services through electronic media. This technology provides fast and affordable internet connectivity to people worldwide without requiring a license. One variation of wireless networks in the third layer, the network layer, is Ad Hoc networks. In such networks, nodes exhibit dynamicity and mobility, leading to rapid changes in network topology. In this network, every node will serve as both a host and a router; however, the dynamic nature of these nodes will result in frequent changes in the network's topology. Ad hoc networks have numerous potential applications and are particularly valuable in various fields. These networks are beneficial in battlefield operations, disaster recovery efforts (e.g., earthquake, flood, and fire), emergency missions, home networking, conferences, and conventions where information sharing is crucial. In military communications, data acquisition and virtual classroom applications in hostile environments are suitable for setting up contacts in exhibitions, coordinating defenses or attack strategies on the battlefield, and facilitating information sharing among airport terminal workers.

Issues in the field of MANETS are as follows:

- (a) Congestion Control
- (b) Dynamic Topology
- (c) Frequent Path Breakage
- (d) Link Stability
- (e) Mobility
- (f) Power Management
- (g) QOS (Quality of Service)
- (f) Reliability
- (g) Routing
- (h) Security

**Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy
Efficiency In Wireless Network**

destination based on the hops' availability. The next hop for packet forwarding is determined based on the source route within the packet. AODV is generally easier to implement and has lower network overhead, while DSR allows for more flexible and efficient route discovery without relying on periodic broadcasts for routing information maintenance.

AODV and DSR do not consider metrics that depend on power, such as the network nodes' lifetime or energy dissipation by participating nodes. For solving this issue, power will be considered when making routing decisions in an ad hoc network.

Pushparaj R et al. (2014). Patil M et al. (2015) and Chawda K et al. (2015) [18, 19, 22] developed Energy2AODV, an energy-efficient AODV that incorporates the Expand Ring Search (ERS) technique for route discovery, effectively reducing energy consumption by avoiding duplicate rebroadcasting of RREQ packets. They carried out the research using AODV as the base protocol. (Krung M et al., 2002) [33] Enhances the capability of AODV by utilizing power-based path selection. When a link breaks in an AODV-enabled network, a RERR message is triggered. The node-detecting link break broadcasts the RERR message to its neighbors, who propagate it further until all nodes with a route through the broken link must get notified. After receiving the RERR message, the route discovery process initiates to check another possible route to the destination based on available neighboring nodes. This protocol calculates the number of hops covered by the data packet and the number of remaining hops to be traveled. If the number of traveled hops exceeds the remaining hops, it enables an energy booster path; otherwise, it selects an alternate path. Under high network load, this protocol exhibits good performance. The authors (Tavosian et al., 2012) [4] applied network coding in the ANC scheme to improve AODV's energy consumption. The authors combined network coding with the AODV routing process, reducing energy consumption and data transmission. Additionally, they introduced a buffering mechanism in intermediate nodes to store incoming packets, combined them with the coding scheme, and forwarded the combination.

The authors (Huang et al., 2011) [5] modify the gossip algorithm implemented on AODV to address high congestion issues. They consider the remaining power of a node in the RREQ and then make the decisions using the gossiping probability. Sun, W., Zhang [6] modify AODV for unidirectional ad hoc networks by employing a backup strategy that computes multiple paths. (Thanthry, N. et al., 2006) [7] discussed the EM-AODV protocol that considers three parameters: battery level, bandwidth, and signal strength when making routing decisions. This protocol uses a multiple-route technique but selects the route based on the node's minimum affinity, available bandwidth, and maximum consumed battery power. Periodically, each node updates this information and chooses the route with the maximum residual battery unless it deems it unfit, in which case it discards it. (Gwalani, S. et al., 2003) [8] discussed AODV-PA (AODV with path accumulation) to enhance the effectiveness of the flooding mechanism by utilizing distributed routed information. The authors (Shibao et al., 2010) [10] presented HP-ERS-AODV, which predicts the latest location of the destination node by studying the patterns of wireless devices attached to humans. Utilizing time-to-live values reduces the retransmission of request messages. The authors (Dargahi et al., 2008) [11] modified AODV and introduced SP-AODV, where they added a flag value to the RREQ packet. They also included two constants, MinTH and MaxTH, which control the value of a new field called the counter in the routing table. The counter value is incremented or decremented based on the constant values, indicating the estimated time for a node to reach the destination. Demir et al. (2007) [12] discuss an auction-based protocol for end-to-end routing to avoid wastage of the source's resources. Considering parameters like digital currency and current energy, implementing the Vickery auction increases the bid when the energy level decreases, and vice versa. However, selfish behavior does not guarantee favorable outcomes. (Sethi S et al., 2009) [13] IMAODV combines AODV and MAODV, which supports multicasting and reliability in a large network area. This protocol establishes bi-directional shared multicasting trees if the group members remain within the connected network. (Thanthry N et al., 2006) [7] proposed using the EM-AODV algorithm to increase the lifespan of networks. This algorithm considers the energy levels of nodes to optimize their usage.

3. OBJECTIVES :

The research objectives of this scholarly Article are listed below:

- (1) To Analyze energy usage in MANETs by studying node mobility, communication traffic, and protocol characteristics.
- (2) To develop energy-efficient routing algorithms using computer networking and optimization principles.
- (3) To evaluate trade-offs between energy conservation and network performance using simulation.
- (4) To create energy-aware routing guidelines and communicate findings to network practitioners and researchers

4. PROPOSED APPROACH :

The primary objective aims to ensure energy efficiency and stability in the route. By seamlessly integrating, it modifies the AODV protocol. It specifically caters to different levels of data traffic and comprises two significant phases: the Route Request Phase (RREQ) and the RREP phase. In this modified version of AODV, every node updates its routing table with new power-related information. The node's battery status is categorized into various levels, with the critical battery status being the lowest or most precarious state, rendering the node ineligible for inclusion. On the other hand, the Active state indicates that the battery has a higher value than a specified threshold. When a new route is required, the system assesses the node's status and establishes the route accordingly.

Route Establishment: This algorithm facilitates the selection of an appropriate sequence of nodes via the path for the requesting party.

Session:

- (1) Initially, $P_i = 0$
- (2) For each valid path P_i
- (3) For each node N_i in P_i
- (4) IF current battery status = Active state
- (5) Then
- (6) Include node in the path and broadcast RREQ to the intermediate nodes N_i .
- (7) End IF
- (8) At the source node S, Scan all RREPs
- (9) RREP with the shortest active route and CURRENT Battery STATUS > MIN_ BATTERY is selected
- (10) Forward data
- (11) Else
- (12) Exclude node from the path
- (13) Then
- (14) Sent RREQ to the selected node
- (15) Then
- (16) Forward the RREQ on the available active route
- (17) Destination node D sends back RREP on the reverse path
- (18) Source node S receives RREP
- (19) Route is established
- (20) The established route forwards data
- (21) End For
- (22) End For

4. SIMULATION SCENARIO :

We incorporated the above methodology into AODV by adding battery status to change its format. We conducted a simulation to study and analyze the operations of the M_AODV. The simulation used NS-2 (Dattana et al., 2019; Gouda et al., 2013) [15, 28]. During the simulation study, we considered the following metrics: E2E delay, throughput, PDR, and the sending and receiving of control packets.

Table 1: Simulation Scenario with Parameter Value

Simulation Parameters	Parameter Value
Simulator	NS-2.32
Simulation Area	700mts × 700mts

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

**Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy
Efficiency In Wireless Network**

frequency allocation techniques can lead to an improved packet delivery ratio in dense networks. However, it is essential to note that the number of nodes does not solely determine the packet delivery ratio; various factors like wireless channel conditions, mobility, power, and network bandwidth also cause AODV exhibits low and unstable packet delivery ratios, Modi_AODV demonstrate better and consistently stable performance. Significantly impact the network performance and packet delivery ratio. Figure 3 illustrates the comparison between AODV and Modi_AODV regarding the Packet Delivery Ratiometric. While AODV exhibits low and unstable packet delivery ratios, Modi_AODV demonstrates better and consistently stable performance.

In MANET, the discovery and establishment of routes between nodes rely on Route Request (RREQ) and Route Reply (RREP) packets. When a source node lacks a route to a destination, it initiates the process by broadcasting an RREQ packet containing relevant information like source and destination addresses, a unique broadcast ID, and the source node's current sequence number. The receiving nodes forward the RREQ packet unless the end node or the nodes already forwarded the same RREQ based on the broadcast ID and source address are reached. Once the end node or an intermediate node with a fresher route to the destination reaches, it sends back a Route Reply (RREP) packet to the source node. The RREP packet contains essential details such as the destination, source addresses, and the destination's current sequence number. The RREQ/RREP packets can set a hop count as a constraint, avoiding loops and limiting the broadcast domain's size to ensure that the packets do not exceed a specific hop count. Additionally, the time-to-live (TTL) field in the RREQ/RREP packets prevents further forwarding when its TTL value reaches zero.

Fig. 4: Send Control Packets (RREQ/ REPLY) using various Numbers of Nodes [100]

Figure 4 demonstrates a performance comparison between AODV and Modi_AODV regarding the number of Control Packets transmitted. The graph illustrates that in Modi_AODV, the sent Control packets increase with the increment of the nodes.

**Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy
Efficiency In Wireless Network**

**Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy
Efficiency In Wireless Network**

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

**Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy
Efficiency In Wireless Network**

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

50% more power than today's systems, which will need more robust power supplies and more bandwidth to support the increased load [12].

The second step in energy efficiency is to improve the energy awareness of all devices in the network. The higher the energy awareness, the higher the network's energy efficiency will be. The energy efficiency of a wireless network depends on its power consumption. This can be achieved by adjusting the transmit power or by enabling node aggregation. In addition to this, adaptive wireless devices are capable of preventing retransmissions. Delay tolerance can greatly increase the life of sensor nodes and therefore reduce the amount of power required by the network [1].

Lastly, the network topology can vary with single-hops, multi-hops, dense or sparse networks. The topology affects the energy consumption of nodes, and it may be better to use a star topology instead of a hierarchical structure. Different channels can be used for data packets and out of band wake up signals can help reduce energy usage. For example, the frequency of the radio waves can be adjusted network [13].

Besides energy efficiencies, network's reliability can also be considered. The more nodes and antennas, the more power they require. Moreover, the density of the network and the amount of traffic will determine its optimal sleep time. The more dense a wireless network is, the more energy it will save per unit of bandwidth. But in addition to this, network reliability and security are other factors of energy efficiency [10].

The energy efficiency of a wireless network is dependent on the higher with more energy they will consume. For example, when the number of sensors in a wireless network is greater, the less power they will need to power the nodes [8]. Further, this type of networking also requires more power, which will increase the cost of the service. Thus, the greater the energy efficiency of a wireless network, the better it is for the environment [14].

Figure 2 Extractor of Vitality & Energy storage

Figure 3 Sensor Node Architecture

IV. ANALYSIS

The New Strategy to Achieve Security and Energy Efficiency in Wireless Networks aims to reduce the number of wireless nodes and increase their density. This can be achieved by deploying large antenna arrays at each base station. By doing this, a network can cover a larger area with less power consumption. Massive MIMO takes advantage of the fact that many antennas are needed to cover a smaller base [11].

The physical-layer approach to security is a promising approach. This technique does not rely on the assumption that the attacker has limited computational power. Instead, it prevents the attacker from detecting and interpreting the messages. In other words, this method is secure because it prevents both security and energy efficiency problems [12]. By implementing the strategy, network operators will be able to create a more secure and energy-efficient wireless network [13].

This new strategy will help networks reduce their energy consumption without compromising security. As mobile devices continue to grow exponentially, the number of wireless networks will grow. This means that current network architectures will not be able to keep pace with the demand for bandwidth and power. Moreover, the cost of running a wireless network will be astronomical. The solution to this problem is to scale up the network. The main goal of this strategy is to reduce the energy consumed and provide high quality of service for small-scale deployments [14].

How various tactics may boost wireless networks power generation, reliability + resilience based on Analysis

As the demand for wireless networks grows, the need for new energy and security solutions is evident. One of the major challenges is the energy consumption of secure services. However, there are new techniques that can improve energy efficiency and security, and can be implemented in existing network infrastructure. The following factor explores some of these techniques [11].

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

optimal number. In both MOPSO and CS, the maximum number of charger nodes is found. The proposed algorithms improve the utility of the charging network and reduce the number of nodes [12].

The proposed algorithm can handle dynamic energy demands and cover three times more nodes than traditional cuckoo search. As a result, it reduces the number of charger nodes while increasing the receiving power of sensor nodes. It also reduces the number of nodes, thereby maximizing the utility of the network [20].

Conserving vitality WSN

To affect the overall performance existing WSNS, a number of techniques can be used. The first technique is to use an energy efficient protocol to reduce energy consumption during network activity [5]. The second technique is to use a power management scheme to switch off node components when not needed. The proposed techniques can help to reduce energy consumption and maintain high data accuracy. Several energy saving methods are discussed in this article. The next two techniques can also be applied to wireless sensor networks [11].

The first technique involves using a hierarchical cluster-based structure. The sensor nodes are grouped together into clusters and a coordinator acts as cluster head. The latter is responsible for coordinating the cluster and forwarding data. Rotating selection considered a good way to balance energy consumption. The second technique is to use a dense-deployment scheme and display temporal and spatial correlations [9].

The second technique involves employing an energy-efficient routing protocol. This protocol conserves network energy builds a minimum spanning tree with a root as a central hub (CH). This reduces energy dissipation during long-distance transmission [6]. In addition, the protocol also minimizes the number of connections between nodes, thereby enabling low-power operation [3].

Wireless detector network

The Wireless detector network is a distributed system of electronic nodes that communicate with each other by means of wireless data connections. It is a promising alternative to conventional methods such as manual sampling and laboratory testing [1]. The network uses transmit data to top user. The cost of a single node is a significant factor in the overall cost of the network. The proposed information routing formula also takes into account the in-network aggregation formula to reduce the overall cost of the network [2].

In order to achieve this goal, the WSN uses small routers with detectors that are able to perform native computations and communicate with alternative sensor nodes. In addition, the device includes a fault node recovery algorithm that combines a genetic and grade diffusion algorithm to find a dead node and shortest path. The algorithm considers the average delay and packet delivery ratio to determine the most appropriate route. For large-scale networks, multiple detectors can be placed in different locations for increased coverage [3].

The Wireless Sensor Network requires battery power and is suited for long-term outdoor use. In addition, the network is able to cover a wide area. The detection range of this network is up to 300 feet. When deploying the network, it is crucial to set up a group of wireless detectors. Each wireless detector has a red activation wheel. Once activated, the device will show a green LED for 1 second and a red LED for three seconds [7].

Energy-effective routing protocols

In network environments, energy-effective routing protocols are used to minimize the amount of traffic on the network. Compared to conventional routing protocols, such as RIP, these protocols use less energy to ensure high-quality service. This article will provide a brief overview of these protocols. The following section contains an explanation of the basic idea behind them. This article also outlines the advantages and disadvantages of these protocols. It is important to understand the basic concept of these protocols to make sure that they are suitable for your organization [19].

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

I	An overview of	1123	The creators devised a network protocol	When compared to	It only provides for
---	----------------	------	---	------------------	----------------------

	game theoretic				
6	Comprehensive Study of Energy efficient and Power Losses in Wireless Personal Area Networking	Ullaha, et al., 2022	The EECS algorithm is a predictive model that determines Routing table with the least amount of energy. On the basis of initial energy, a steady set of possible sensor nodes are chosen and compete for the status of cluster - head.	Creates a balance point depending on energy and distance between intra-cluster energy demand and inter-cluster communications demand.	Long-distance broadcasts from Cluster heads will consume a lot of energy. As a result, it is unsuitable for long-distance networks.

V. CONCLUSION

Increasing demand for security and energy efficiency are two major concerns for the wireless network industry. As the number of mobile devices increases and the cost of deploying base stations continues to rise, energy-efficient solutions have become essential. Using small base stations in wireless networks can drastically reduce energy consumption, and at the same time enhance network performance. This is an important topic that is being discussed more.

In addition to these concerns, the growing volume of wireless traffic is likely to increase exponentially in the next few years, making energy efficiency and security a top priority in the WSNS. Likewise, the distribution of visuals through remote technologies seems high and increasing rapidly. This is why this research seeks to develop a new radio resource access scheme that is Quality of Experience aware.

The evaluation of existing wireless networks reveals and the proposed scheme improves performance by reducing energy consumption and packet delay. It also enables low-energy use of radio resources. This scheme can be applied in the field of mobile networks, as it can be widely adopted in the field of mobile networks.

A new strategy to achieve security and energy efficiency in Wireless Network is gaining momentum today, thanks to the growing demand for mobile data. While the current network architecture is largely based on gateway nodes and connects these to the rest of the internet, new network topologies can help address these challenges. By eliminating the need for separate access points, a single access point can save energy and increase coverage.

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

- [11] Cheng, W. and Yange, B., (2022). Evaluation of the Energy Consumption of an e-Commerce Business Relationship monitoring e-business Network Built on Handheld Cloud Applications Developing software in Science, 2022.
- [12] Chochoiourou, A.H, Kourtiss, L.G., Spiliopoulou, C.X., Lazaridis, I., Zahariss, K., Zarakoovitis, S. & Kourtise, F., (2021). Considerations about energy saving and tendencies in upcoming 5G deep learning architectures Frequencies, 15(18), p.5395.
- [13] Caos, L., Yuei, Y. and Zhange, Y., (2021). Towards Energy-Efficient and Collaboration Optimization-Based Intelligence Gathering Tactic for Multilingual IoT Devices, Research journal.
- [14] Ivoghlians, A., Salcici, Z. and Wange, K.I.K., (2022). Adaptive Wireless Network Management with Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning. *Sensors*, 22(3), p.1019.
- [15] Moore, S.F., Rosenthal, E.W., Smiths, T.Y. and Reynolds, B.F., (2021). Responsive Inductive Charging Transmission and Multispectral Connectivity for Rechargeable Visual cortex Implants that Operate Indefinitely, *Procedia*, 110(1), pp.89-106.
- [16] Pirouzie, S., Zaghians, M., Aghaeie, J., Chabook, H., Abbassi, M., Norouzie, M., Shafie-khahan, M. and Catalão, J.P., (2022). Integrated decentralized power utilities robotic ramping up safety and operational KPIs, *Journals of Electronic engineering Power and Energy Systems*, 138, p.107540.
- [17] Lims, J., Normman, B.A. and Rajgopals, L., (2022). Immunotherapeutic infrastructures must be redesigned. *Proceedings in Analytical Internationally Interactions in Parametric Studies*, 30(2), pp.200-225.
- [18] Zouu, B., Penge, C., Gu, B., Lei, R., Yann, Z. and Yange, K., (2022). The comparison of dynamically scripting language and commandment operating methodologies for office space energy Power system. *Power generation Utilization*, 305, p.117875.
- [19] Nagendranth, M.V.S.S., Khannai, M.R., Krishnarajan, N., Sikkanddar, M.Y., Aboameir, M.A. and Surendrani, R., (2022). With cryptography in nodes, a subunit distorted clustered protocols with enhanced amoeba swarm cache coherency networking. *The Journal of Supercomputing*, pp.1-19.
- [20] Wange, Z., Liue, J., Zhange, Y., Yuan, H., Zhong, R. and Srinivasani, M.K., (2021). Philosophical dilemmas in using device frameworks for sustainable buildings: Traveling through roadblocks Assessments of Alternative energy, 145, p.110969.
- [21] Yousef M.A.A.E., Dattana V. (2021) Auto Attendance Smartphones Application Based on the Global Positioning System (GPS). In: Arai K. (eds) *Advances in Information and Communication. FICC 2021. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol 1363. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-73100-7_63

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Tracking Students' Progress using Big Data Analytics to enhance student's Employability: A Review

Anfal Al Yousufi, Vikas Rao Naidu, Karan Jesrani, and Vishal Dattana
Department of Computing, Middle East College, Muscat, Oman

[anfal@ mec.edu.om, vikas@mec.edu.om, kjesrani@mec.edu.om, vishal@mec.edu.om]

www.mec.edu.om

Abstract

The amount of data made available is enormous. Hence having a way to track both learners' progress and enable the institutions to identify and track their success rate, status, achievements, and weakness in comparison to other benchmarked institutions would allow them to be more proactive and progressive. Benchmarking would help check the performance rate of their learners, faculty and curriculum performance against similar ones for better insights into potential future enhancements. The end result would be to enable decision makers to detect, analyse, understand and predict the following: education progress, learners' behaviour, and course outcomes. This research paper will provide an insight on various aspects of Big Data Analytics (BDA), for the above purpose by reviewing various practices being followed. Finally, authors will provide recommendations for successful implementation of BDA to track students' performance and take necessary actions. This will be helpful in tracking their academic progress and hence enhance their employability skills by identifying the areas of improvements.

Keywords: Big Data Technology, Big Data Analysis, e-learning, decision making, employability.

1. Introduction

Big data technology helps the institution to track and identify their success rate and help analyze their business situation, key performance indicators (KPI) and academic accreditation. This would help them to provide evidence of their success rate and identify areas of improvements which would allow them to make more proactive and progressive decisions. Benchmarking would enable decision makers to detect, analyze and predict which would help them identify the learners' weaknesses, strengths and predicting who might fail or pass. As per Bichsel, "education needs investment in analytics professionals who contribute to defining the key questions throughout all process till developing data models to design and deliver alerts, recommendations, dashboards, and reports" Being able to do analysis would help with clustering and grouping based on learning difficulties and interaction patterns, and on the other hand, Big Data Technology implementation would help with educational data mining and learning analytics. It would also help methods of education.

The role of data in educational environments is evolving personalize education and enhance learning, teaching and assessments in comparison to the traditional and has the very potential to affect institutions, students and suppliers. Hence, making sure privacy is at the top priority while doing data analysis of the students results / Performance.

Modern universities employ student data to comprehend students' educational experiences. As a result, teachers are able to instruct students more effectively. In order to provide pupils with a well-rounded learning strategy, big data is also employed to change the educational system. (UpGrad, 2022).

The most advanced method for gathering, allocating, completing, and discovering large datasets is known as big data. Larger datasets are used. It uses a variety of patterns to anticipate data. Education and big data have a lot in common. This is due to the fact that educational big data offers a number of applications that support innovative teaching practices, effective educational administration, and effective research management (UpGrad, 2022). Educational institutions must deal with student data much as businesses must deal with a lot of data pertaining to their customers, partners, staff, and financials. Huge amounts of data are created each year when thousands of students enroll in a variety of courses at various institutes. The course information, enrollment year, student ID, exam grades, and marks earned in each topic are all included in the student data. For the advancement of their jobs, analysis of this data can be quite helpful.

2. Literature Review

Educational institutes must treat the education process as an incomplete solution and thus should be treated as a research problem (Humboldt 1970). The methods for involving students in inquiry-based learning are interdependent (Healey and Jenkins 2009). Only blended learning can accomplish this (Gebre Yohannes et al. 2016) (Hasan et al. 2015) (Siddiqui et al. 2012), yet even that is insufficient. It is important to record information regarding learners and the learning process. EDM (Educational Data Mining) and Learning Analytics are a result of this (LA). Learning analytic

will be used in this case to monitor, gather, examine, and present the report data of individual students (Hadhrami 2017) and show continuous development of the undergraduates throughout the planned module (Shute, 2008), assist instructor in disseminating discovery, and assist administrators in forecasting future enrolment.

For comprehending and enhancing educational activity and the conditions in that takes place, analytics about learning means the process of measuring, collection, examination, and disseminating of information on students and their circumstances (Siemens & Gašević, 2012).

A number of studies in the learning area have lately been conducted with the goal of increasing the student's effort on the various educational activities. The improvement of the educational system has facilitated the finest possible growth of education in both students and teachers. Every aspect of the educational area, including design and implementation, is covered by the structural approach. The goal of this research was to make the education approach better for both teachers and students. The data from the Learning Management System is the primary focus of learning analytics (LMS).

Utilizing a learning management system has the advantage of aiding in the growth and enhancement of teaching and learning in an appropriate way. Learning analytics is becoming more and more important and well-liked. It is based on data from remote sources. There is also the theory that learning is dependent on LMS. It is typical for knowledge-embedding examined information on LMS to disregard tasks that originate from external sources, leading to the perception that only a minimal amount of a student's involvement in education is being considered.

The second claim shows that the system is designed with administrators' authority in mind rather than that of the pupils and teachers. Learning analytics therefore places less emphasis on individuals and more on educational measurement.

A project called Uatu has researched using data visualiser to ascertain the activities of the pupil involvement through the module content because the system has certain challenges identifying trackable contributions. The students collaborate to contribute to and keep information in the Google Drive sheets. These Google's documents provide a set of information on the students' work, including a list of edits and the content that each edit added. The study comes to the conclusion that no comments can be taken and obtained through the

data collecting. Students are therefore unable to provide appropriate group engagement. The end result demonstrates that locating the analytics can be challenging and that the system may be shut off.

According to Michael Wesch's observation, which he made after using a portion of the issue he was having to evaluate the development of the knowledge transfer services, the observer's goal was to establish the connection from inquiries to questions. Other strategy was by concentrating on teaching analytics and have the students interact with their own data. The system's efforts are explained to the pupils, along with how it will reflect on their actions in order to spot problematic behavior. As a result, learning analytics will help the researcher fully comprehend how the system is progressing. It focuses on how students perform, reflect, and respond in order to discover how students' behavior changes as a result of their comprehension.

Learning analytics, according to Hadhrami, are not a recent development; they have roots in various corporate intelligence and educational domains. The growing volume of high-quality data is a result of students taking part in various educational processes all across the world. Learning analytics' goals are to obtain knowledge, collect data, and adjust the educational system; as a result, they will help teachers use and develop their ways of transferring and seeking knowledge to give as many types as possible of problems that students need to practice and learn from (Hadhrami 2017).

Data from learning management systems are the primary focus of learning analytics (LMS). The information from the Learning Management System features showing figure of how many times each student has accessed the pages, student evaluation in accordance with the course pre-requirements, duration of students accessing the reading materials, duration of assessment completions, and participation in forum debates.

This cannot be sufficient in the rapidly altering world; visual analysis data employing video-streaming servers can bring additional advantages in addition to LMS, giving stakeholders more capability for better prediction, increasing pupil's achievement aspect, and optimizing learning and learner experience. The two analytics will be strengthened by blended learning, which will also favor research-based learning.

Dashboards offer real-time visualization that enhances student performance while saving teachers' time and efforts by giving students the

knowledge and tools they need to succeed. By giving learners and teachers the tools they need to assess their progress and attain the greatest outcomes, learning objectives are achieved more quickly. The benefit of learning analytics helps teachers improve instruction and learning so that students comprehend concepts clearly (Eckerson 2011). Additionally, learning analytics aids and assists educational establishments in enhancing student performance. The development of sound knowledge is based on the educational models that have been adopted by the learning analytics and data mining communities in educational institutions.

Students can be given numerous options in modern classrooms to learn content in various ways. Additionally, they have a variety of ways to provide access to the materials (Uskov 2016). With the help of different technical advancements like the Learning Management System (LMS) and the streaming server, these classes' learning environments are improved. These technological advancements make it easier to provide active classroom instruction, which is a component of blended learning.

LMS is used to provide a standardized condition for data communication, if it's for an evaluation or an activity for online students. High-quality video can be used for concurrent playback with a fair degree of latency thanks to streaming servers. Learning analytics is the process of analyzing and mining data that has been collected from the streaming server and LMS logs. Possible LA goals, which is surveillance, examination, future estimation, modifications, evaluation, check-up, adaptation, customisation, recommending points, and considerations, can be accomplished in this environment (Chatti et al. 2012).

In some ways, teaching is a creative endeavor where information is transferred to students through the arts. It's a teacher's responsibility to spread knowledge in the classroom using the most effective techniques. The teacher's job is to determine the needs of the students and any obstacles to learning they may be facing. Simulators are used in computer hardware instruction to help students comprehend it better by showing them how the hardware functions from the inside out (Hasan & Mahmood, 2012) (Siddiqui, Hasan, Mahmood, & Khan, 2012) (Kazmi, Hayat, Hasan, & Dattana, 2017). The learning experience for students is improved by employing blended learning, which requires the integration of both theoretical and practical concepts. help enhance the discovery learning process by allowing students to quickly perceive and understand examples. Students' learning experiences are improved by

integrating technology and multimedia applications, for instance GeoGebra for the analysis of statistical and mathematical side (Gebreyohannes, Bhatti, & Hasan, 2016) (Bhatti, Hasan, Farsi, & Kazmi, 2017). Some tried learning that is based on activity, where the teacher watched the effects of teaching and learning, to improve student engagement and learning experiences (Hayat, Hasan, Ali, & Kaleem, 2017). The design of the learning environment promotes the finest teaching methods and maximizes student engagement (Bhatia & Naidu, 2017) (Naidu, Singh, Hasan, & Hadrami, 2017). Applications for interaction are used to deepen students' grasp of foundational ideas (Raweehi, Ansari, Udipi, & Naidu, 2017) (Farsi, Udipi, & Naidu, 2017). Instructors can quickly get used to and improve the process of transferring knowledge and getting knowledge (Naidu, Balushi, & Bhatia, 2017) by using games or tech-based education thanks to the important role that open-source tools play in education (Naidu, Singh, Harrasi, & Balushi, 2017). In their paper (Puka et al, 2020) present an experimental investigation of multidimensional relationships in online learning. Their efforts are directed at making sure the students are happy with the e-learning procedures. They used data gathered from the Bosnia and Herzegovina region to inform the survey they performed for their study. They employed the random sample method, selecting 11 BiH higher education institutions, and giving the students questionnaires. Confirmative factor analysis was used to examine and identify the data once the replies from the students were received. The well-structured mathematical models were operated to validate the model.

They have demonstrated in their research that the metacognitive strategies variable directly influences the satisfaction of the students while using e-learning, while the motivation, inclination, and goal setting variables, along with the environment structuring and communal scopes, indirectly affect the students' satisfaction. They have provided a plan of action for the advancement of e-learning based on the research they did. In their study, they offered eight hypotheses. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and structural equation model analysis (SEM) have been utilized to generate the hypotheses and model their study. They have been using the Lisrel 8.8 program for analysis. The Cronbach's Alpha (CA) indicator was used to assess the reliability of the measurement scale. The SPSS 20 program's correlation analysis was used to examine the relationships between the variables.

The interaction between the learner and a specific instructional environment is the focus of the most

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

Evaluation And Development Of New Strategy To Achieve Security And Energy Efficiency In Wireless Network

9

Blockchain in Healthcare: A Systematic Review and Future Perspectives

Arpneek Kaur¹, Sandhya Bansal², and Vishal Dattana³

¹Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Maharishi Markandeshwar Engineering College, Maharishi Markandeshwar Deemed to be University, India;

Email: arpneek.kaur@mmumullana.org

²Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Maharishi Markandeshwar Engineering College, Maharishi Markandeshwar Deemed to be University, India;

Email: sandhyabansal@mmumullana.org

³Department of Computer Engineering, Middle East College, Sultanate of Oman;

Email: vishaldattana@gmail.com

Abstract

Healthcare, being a basic necessity and a fundamental human right, is a paramount discipline of research today. During the past decade, blockchain technology has gained an increased interest from academic scholars for its use in the healthcare sector. Applications such as healthcare supply chain, identification of fake drugs, managing and securing electronic health records, managing patient appointments with healthcare providers, regular patient monitoring using various tools, and telemedicine come into picture with respect to healthcare. A thorough survey of related research works in this domain is required in order to gain insights into the future ideas and recommendations for the use of blockchain technology in the healthcare sector. In this book chapter, we aim to provide an exhaustive systematic review of research publications related to smart healthcare applications by the use of blockchain technology. With a thorough review and study of the research works selected by systematic approach, this book chapter aims

212 *Blockchain in Healthcare: A Systematic Review and Future Perspectives*

to answer a set of research questions focusing on blockchain platforms, consensus methods, smart contracts, system evaluation methods, and their drawbacks. A tabular comparison of all the research articles on the basis of the research questions is provided. In the end, we give our observations of the challenges and limitations of the research works under this study, and their possible solutions. Thus, we reach up to a future scope of blockchain technology in healthcare applications.

9.1 Introduction

Healthcare is the focused area of research today as the world has witnessed widespread illnesses like the COVID-19 pandemic in the last two years. Researchers today are proposing and publishing their healthcare systems in large numbers in order to match the need of the hour. Modern healthcare systems are making use of state-of-the-art technologies in order to make diagnosis and treatment better in all ways. When it comes to modern healthcare machines, testing machines, and software, each has a common requirement that they need to store some or other sort of data. As the size of this data grows, it becomes equally important to maintain the integrity of this data, the accuracy, and access rights of this data because it is the integrity of this data which builds a trust between the participating entities – like the patients, the healthcare providers, the hospitals, the law bodies, etc. Blockchain technology comes with its own unique features like trust, integrity, immutability, non-repudiation, and authentication, which are required in all cases mentioned above. Blockchain technology became first known by its use in the Bitcoin cryptocurrency. Bitcoin is only a cryptocurrency and allows only the transactions of bitcoins. Gradually, the same technology became applicable to other real-world systems like in real estate, voting systems, insurance systems, secure chat rooms, supply chain systems, the very famous NFTs, and healthcare systems [49] not being an exception. This rise in the usage of blockchain systems has only taken a decade, owing to its very benefits which can be applicable in each and every domain. There is a huge amount of literature in the past five years containing new blockchain-based healthcare system models. Recognizing a need for an exhaustive review of all such quality works aims to provide the same in this book chapter. The field of blockchain technology is very diverse with its varied choices of platforms, consensus rules, and system features each providing different sets of characteristics. This book chapter contributes to the academicians by providing a comparative picture of the use of different elements of blockchain

technology in recent literature works related to healthcare. At the end, it also derives some open challenges and future scope in this field. Thus, it shows a path to new blockchain-enabled research works in healthcare domain. The remaining part of this article has been organized as follows. Section 9.2 provides some applications and challenges in the modern healthcare industry which can be successfully dealt with the blockchain technology. In Section 9.3, an introduction to the blockchain technology and its important elements has been provided. Next, we provide the research methodology for selection of literature works in Section 9.4. Section 9.5 provides a theoretical literature review of the selected articles. In Section 9.6, we mention the findings of this exhaustive review based on the research questions in the form of tables and pie charts. Section 9.7 provides some open challenges and future scope for the use of blockchain technology in healthcare, followed by conclusion in Section 9.8.

9.2 Healthcare Challenges vs. Blockchain Opportunities

Today, blockchain technology is being successfully employed in numerous practical applications of varied domains, healthcare being one of them. Within the healthcare domain, there can be seen various applications of blockchain technology as shown in Figure 9.1.

Modern healthcare applications pose a lot of challenges due to the very evolving nature of technology today. Each new technique comes with its own set of challenges when it comes to practical implementation. Blockchain technology has evolved as a rescue to some of the important challenges in healthcare domain. In Figure 9.2, we mention some of the important healthcare challenges and explain how blockchain helps in solving them.

9.2.1 Interoperability

Patients as of now have no control or own responsibility for their clinical information, which makes it almost outlandish for data to be divided between various medical clinics. Moreover, security, trust, credibility, and responsibility issues demolish the circumstance for patients. Blockchain gives an option in contrast to the current detached cycle for gathering and putting away persistent information. A stage that depends on blockchain and is divided among patients, emergency clinics, and other medical care parties contains permanent, secure, and recognizable information, tackling the issue with legitimacy. Simultaneously, the information put away on a blockchain

Figure 9.1 Blockchain in healthcare applications.

can undoubtedly be pseudonymized, tackling the issue with patient ID. In the blockchain-based model, patients and their clinical information are at the focal point of medical care. This implies that more control and proprietorship is allowed to patients – they get to conclude who can get and peruse their clinical information containing ailment, medicine, lab tests, medical history, etc., in the form of EHRs [17]. Simultaneously, medical clinics can all the more effectively access shared data and give better consideration and worth to the patient. With the ascent of IoT and information accumulated from wearables or portable applications, the issue with information interoperability turns out to be increasingly significant [18]. Blockchain is a chance to settle it.

9.2.2 Tampering/data security

Since there is no central entity in a blockchain system, an agreement among all members should be reached before any information gets refreshed or added to the framework. Saving every one of the details behind the agreement calculations, this implies that the framework stores changeless path of all collaborations at any point made. One of the serious issues in medical care on a worldwide scale is the absence of all around perceived patient identifiers

Figure 9.2 Healthcare challenges vs. blockchain opportunities.

[53]. Indeed, even arrangements like EHR cannot totally take care of this issue and have, previously, brought about jumbling of patient records. Blockchain, then again, gives the essential components to producing secure and reliable clinical records, which are difficult to get undermined or altered on the grounds that every communication in the framework at any point made passes on a review trail so that everyone might see [16]. Essentially, blockchain could tackle one more large issue in medical care, for example, oversee clinical preliminary information, while consenting to guidelines. Since clinical preliminaries as a rule require long responsibility and weighty venture, there is a danger of having the eventual outcomes changed or altered for different uses like fraudulent insurance claims [83], misuse of drugs [74], etc. In any case, defiling preliminary information is almost inconceivable in a universally open information stage that gives changeless path, all things considered. Besides, preliminary members can be compensated for following the arrangement intently, guaranteeing a drawn out responsibility.

9.2.3 Insurance fraud

Debasing clinical preliminary outcomes is not the main misrepresentation from which the medical care industry endures. An issue on a more noteworthy scale is battling protection extortion [85]. Blockchain can assist with forestalling bogus case sections by patients or potential suppliers by basically putting away all exchanges safely, giving detectability of every exchange.

Figure 9.3 Block structure with Merkle root.

to the transactions held on the network between different parties or on the data itself. Each block may contain “n” number of transactions selected with the help of consensus protocols [69]. The timestamp field contains the time when the block was created. A block created and written to the blockchain once cannot be changed again. The value of nonce is calculated by extensive computations in order to ensure a particular difficulty level of hash. The hash and previous has fields in the block to ensure the immutability of the blocks. Any minute change in the block data immediately reflects in the hash value. If a malicious user tries to add his block inside the blockchain, he needs to calculate the nonce values and hashes for all the subsequent blocks with at least 51% of the nodes of the network. The transactions contained inside a block are arranged in the form of a Merkle tree. Merkle tree contains the hash of each transaction at its leaf nodes. The nodes at each higher level contain the combined hash of previous hashes [61]. Merkle tree facilitates in easier verification and validation of individual transactions without considering the other transactions in the block.

Figure 9.4 Types of blockchain networks.

The root of the Merkle tree, called the Merkle root, is stored within the header of the block. This maintains the integrity and consistency of each and every transaction in the blockchain.

9.3.2 Types of blockchain networks

Blockchain networks can be broadly classified into public and private types according to the accessibility and permissions to join the blockchain network. Other types of networks include permissioned, consortium, hybrid which can be viewed like a hybrid between the public and private networks, each with their own variations as shown in Figure 9.4. Each type of blockchain network has its own set of characteristics, owing to various advantages and disadvantages. One must choose a type of network according to the need of the application for which blockchain is to be employed.

A public blockchain is free to join for anyone. There are full nodes, miner nodes, and wallet nodes in a network according to their computation powers and capacity. There are no constraints on the roles of any node [79]. Some business firms do not like to expose their sensitive data to the world wide nodes on the public blockchain network. In a private network, a business firm decides who will join the network, what type of transactions will be allowed, and what consensus protocols will be used [19]. Permissioned blockchain networks can be employed with a special access control layer which provides particular roles and access rights to the users in the network [2]. Permissioned blockchain networks can be viewed as a mid-way between fully private and fully public blockchains. A consortium blockchain is typically a blockchain network formed by multiple organizations related to the same type of business as in [91] and [93]. There are hybrid blockchain networks that use both the public and private blockchains for different types of data as in [70] and [90].

Figure 9.5 Smart contracts.

9.3.3 Consensus algorithms

The blockchain network consists of a large number of nodes spread across different locations. Each node has its own copy of the distributed ledger. Whenever there is an update for the ledger, it has to be updated the same with all of the nodes on the network. That is why there is a need for some mechanism by which all the nodes of the network can come to an agreement regarding the new block to be added to the blockchain. This mechanism is called “consensus”. A consensus mechanism must not be centralized which will go against the integral properties of blockchain [35]. The nodes of the blockchain network must have equal probability of being able to add their blocks in their blockchain. There are different algorithms used in the blockchains for distributed consensus.

9.3.4 Smart contracts

Smart contracts are small programs that can reside on the blockchain network. The execution of this program code is automatically triggered when certain predefined conditions are met. The smart contracts execute on the nodes of the blockchain network rather than on a central server. Thus, once migrated and deployed to the blockchain network, smart contracts themselves become immutable, and, thus, no party can change and validate the contractual conditions without the consent of the other parties involved [46]. Thus, smart contracts act as a smart substitute for traditional paper contracts and also eliminate the need of a third party such as a lawyer. Smart contracts can be written in any programming language. Some of the common programming languages used for smart contracts are Solidity, Go, Java, JavaScript, Python, etc. Smart contracts provide innumerable benefits like speed, autonomy,

accuracy, transparency, and cost savings. Figure 9.5 shows an example of a healthcare smart contract between a doctor and a patient.

9.4 Research Methodology

As it is a systematic review, it is necessary to select the most relevant papers related to blockchain in healthcare in the year 2017–2021. Various search strategies were formed for this task. This review article has been focused on the following review questions:

- **RQ1:** What type of blockchain network and blockchain platform has been used by researchers in their healthcare applications?
- **RQ2:** What are the important consensus algorithms used in blockchain-based healthcare systems?
- **RQ3:** What proportion of research works have built smart contracts in their healthcare systems and which programming languages have they used?
- **RQ4:** What are the evaluation methods used by researchers for analyzing their models?
- **RQ5:** What are the drawbacks of the existing blockchain systems related to healthcare and what are the future perspectives?

The article selection procedure is shown in Figure 9.6. First, the five most relevant databases, IEEE-Xplore, Science Direct, Springer, Google Scholar, and PubMed, were searched using the various keywords like “Blockchain AND EHR”, “Blockchain AND EMR”, “Blockchain AND Medical Supply Chain”, “Blockchain AND Health Insurance”, “Blockchain AND Drug Supply Chain”, etc. A total of 1980 articles were fetched. After this, a filter on the basis of title scan, removal of duplicates, magazine, conference proceedings, conference papers with pages less than 5, book chapters, and exclusion of review papers were applied and a total 127 papers were selected. Next, this count is reduced to 105 by applying a filtering process on the basis of citation count and quality check. Finally, selection criteria based on abstract scan and review questions were conducted that led to selection of final 90 articles for review.

9.5 Literature Review

The authors in [1] had designed a smart healthcare system with the integration of blockchain 3.0 and healthcare 4.0. The designed network has been implemented in Ethereum network along with other programming languages

revocable attribute scheme to protect privacy. Attribute signing key is calculated with the combination of attribute master key and update master key. The paper [16] proposes a multi-tier architecture for privacy preservation. This novel architecture uses public blockchain between different EHR cloud providers and other between patient sensors and patient systems. The papers [28] and [33] use cryptographic functions for maintaining the pseudonymity of the patient data. The paper [49] uses various utility functions to evaluate privacy preserving frameworks. Multiple smart contracts are used for evaluation of access control and transaction evaluation. The paper [35] uses blockchain for securing decentralized EHR sharing. The work [18] proposes a hybrid architecture that combines blockchain and edge nodes to facilitate EHR access control. This architecture maintains a tamper proof log of the access events. Hyperledger Fabric is used for the evaluation of the hybrid architecture. In addition to this, [19] and [44] also propose a novel EHR framework for trustworthy access control mechanisms between various users of EHR. Ethereum is used for prototype implementation. Furthermore, [20] focuses on patient controlled sharing schemes instead of third parties. Some medical institutes are used for storing the PESchain. These are used for storing the hash values of the encrypted patient record. Stealth authorization scheme is constructed for privacy preservation and sharing of data. The work [21] addresses the problem of privacy preservation and security over cloud sharing of EHR records. Searchable encryption and conditional proxy re-encryption based scheme is developed for the resolution of problems. Proof of authorization is used as a consensus protocol. The paper [24] presents a novel audit mechanism for exchanging e-health data across the borders in Europe, while [47] proposes an architecture for EHR data in Peruvian health organizations. For off-chain storage of medical data and providing logs of transactions, laws maintained by Peruvian are followed. The paper [48] proposes a framework for sharing and management of cancer patients. The data validation is done on the data of Stony Brook University Hospital. The paper [25] presents a blockchain-based solution for secure EHR inter-exchange. Security analysis is done in terms of inside and outside threats on the system. The work [41] proposes a permissioned blockchain for cross-organizational data sharing. The paper [26] proposes a novel and secure scheme named MedSBA, an attribute-based encryption scheme for sharing of EHR. Private blockchain is utilized. The work [27] develops real, operational, and secured PHRs. Three design principles were developed for secure PHR. The work [36] proposes a certificate-less scheme and elliptical curve cryptography scheme for the security of data. The paper [30] integrates Hyperledger blockchain with deep learning for secure data management and diagnosis model, respectively. The

developed model works in five different stages. SIMON block cipher technique is applied for encryption of data and variational autoencoder is applied for detection of disease. The work [31] utilizes smart contracts for sharing of data between patients, doctors, and caretakers. Modified Merkle tree data structure is used for secure and fast access of data. Cryptographic hash functions are used for security of data. The paper [32] uses attribute and identity-based encryption for security of data over the cloud. The paper [37] develops a novel model MedRec for data access and permission management of medical data. The work [39] proposes a granular access control mechanism that can give different levels of authorization while maintaining compatibility with underlying blockchain architecture. The work [45] focuses on the EHR data of emergency wards of the hospitals. This work uses the P2P network for analyzing data transmission of smart contracts. The paper [46] builds a unified solution for migrating the existing EHR. Off-chain storage of assets is controlled through patient and policy transactions.

9.6 Discussion

We have already provided a brief literature review of the selected articles. We can successfully derive the answers to our research questions based on the survey. In this section, we head towards a discussion of our findings on the basis of research questions one by one.

9.6.1 RQ1: What type of blockchain network and blockchain platform has been used by researchers in their healthcare applications?

Table 9.1 Types of blockchain networks in recent works

Type of network	References
Public	[16], [51], [54], [62], [63], [68], [69], [72], [76], [79], [80], [81], [83], [86], [87]
Private	[9], [19], [23], [24], [25], [27], [30], [34], [37], [39], [43], [46], [50], [52], [59], [73], [98]
Hybrid	[3], [18], [26], [57], [66], [67], [70], [75], [90]
Consortium	[20], [21], [22], [32], [38], [40], [44], [47], [56], [58], [61], [77], [82], [85], [88], [91], [93], [98]
Permissioned	[2], [10], [28], [31], [33], [34], [35], [36], [42], [44], [46], [48], [55], [56], [60], [64], [65], [71], [78], [84], [89], [92], [95], [96], [97]

Figure 9.7 Comparison of network types in recent works.

Table 9.2 Blockchain platforms in recent works

Blockchain platform used	References
Hyperledger (Fabric/Burrow/Composer/Iroha/Sawtooth)	[3], [18], [27], [30], [34], [35], [44], [46], [47], [48], [56], [64], [65], [67], [78], [84], [91], [92], [94], [95], [96], [97]
Ethereum	[2], [10], [19], [20], [21], [25], [33], [35], [36], [37], [38], [40], [43], [50], [51], [54], [55], [57], [60], [68], [69], [72], [76], [79], [80], [81], [83], [87], [88], [91], [94]
Developed by authors	[70], [71], [73], [85], [89]
Wanchain	[23]
OPNET	[26]
Multichain	[24]
IOTA	[40]
Cardano	[40]
Bitcoin	[40], [63]
NEM	[75]
QuarkChain	[90]
Gcoin	[93]

The type of platform is chosen by the researchers according to the requirements of the system. Table 9.1 categorizes the reviewed literature works based on the type of network, viz. public, private, hybrid, consortium, and permissioned. Figure 9.7 depicts that researchers prefer to use permissioned systems above all because they provide benefits of access control and role

Figure 9.7 Comparison of blockchain platforms in recent works.

definition. However, we can see that there are lesser number of research works with hybrid systems, which can be viewed as a future scope in this direction owing to the very benefits of public–private hybrids. In Table 9.2 as well as Figure 9.7, we can very well notice that Ethereum is the most widely used platform by the researchers in healthcare domain, with Hyperledger being the second one. However, more research works are needed to find out the performance of varied platforms such as IOTA, Cardano, GCoin, etc. It has also been noticed that only a 7% of researchers have developed their own platforms.

9.6.2 RQ2: What are the important consensus algorithms used in blockchain-based healthcare systems?

Consensus methods are a very important element of a blockchain system. The selection of a good distributed consensus method leads to cost and time savings in the network. The consensus methods used by selected research works have been summarized in Table 9.3. Also, Figure 9.8 shows that proof of work is the most used consensus algorithm till date. More research works are needed with other consensus methods that have lesser cost and computation requirements. Also, there is more scope of new consensus algorithms to be built by authors in future works.

Table 9.3 Consensus algorithms used in recent works

Consensus algorithm	References
Proof of work	[2], [10], [33], [37], [51], [54], [55], [62], [68], [69], [72], [76], [79], [80], [81], [91], [93]
Proof of authority	[21], [40], [50], [60], [90]
Delegated proof of stake	[38], [52], [70], [94]
Created by authors	[30], [32], [58], [85], [95], [98]
Practical byzantine fault tolerance	[26], [44], [48], [61], [64], [84], [91], [94], [97]
Proof of concept	[19], [47]
Proof of stake	[86]
Proof of reputation	[63]
Proof of importance	[75]
Byzantine fault tolerance	[83], [89], [92]
Istanbul byzantine fault tolerance	[35]
Kafka	[65]
Galaxy consensus	[23]

Figure 9.8 Comparison of consensus algorithms in recent works.

9.6.3 RQ3: What proportion of research works have built smart contracts in their healthcare systems and which programming languages have they used?

Smart contracts, being an important element of the newer versions of blockchain, are employed in various healthcare systems for maintaining the integrity, access control, and other security features of the system. However, in Figure 9.9, we see that a huge proportion of about 42% research works are not proposing any smart contracts in their models, which is an important requirement for future systems.

Table 9.4 Smart contract languages in recent works

Programming language	References
Solidity	[2], [10], [19], [21], [25], [33], [35], [37], [38], [43], [50], [51], [55], [57], [60], [68], [69], [72], [76], [79], [80], [81], [86], [95]
ChainCode	[46], [47], [48], [64], [65], [67], [84], [92], [96], [97]
Java Script	[18], [27], [78]
Python	[31], [83], [88]
Swift	[75]
Rust	[3]
Go	[30]

Figure 9.9 Usage of smart contracts in recent works.

Figure 9.10 Comparison of smart contract languages used in recent works.

Table 9.4 summarizes the languages selected by the remaining of the systems for their smart contracts. In Figure 9.10, we can notice that Solidity, being the only smart contract language for Ethereum, is the most widely used, whereas there is a huge future scope of newer smart contract languages like Rust, Go, etc.

9.6.4 RQ4: What are the evaluation methods used by researchers for analyzing their models?

There are different evaluation methods used in research works for analysis of the proposed models. Our finding as shown in Table 9.5 and Figure 9.11 is that a huge proportion, i.e., 46% of works are using performance metrics such as latency, throughput, communication cost, computation cost, transaction time, data size, etc., for the evaluation of their proposed systems. However, lesser researchers are interested towards survey-based evaluation methods, which should also be opted because blockchain, being a new technology, needs to be testified by the end users of the system in order to gain popularity.

9.6.5 RQ5: What are the drawbacks of the existing blockchain systems related to healthcare and what are the future perspectives?

We have come across some common drawbacks of existing systems which need to be addressed in the future works. Table 9.6 summarizes some of the drawbacks identified in the existing systems. We can see that data privacy issues and scalability issues are the most common among the articles under

Table 9.5 System evaluation methods used in recent works

Evaluation method	References
System analysis by discussion of different features like privacy, access control, immutability, transparency, interoperability, etc., depending on proposed models	[2], [20], [23], [25], [28], [37], [39], [42], [44], [46], [47], [48], [52], [54], [55], [58], [61], [66], [67], [68], [69], [70], [72], [75], [76], [77], [79], [80], [82], [84], [86], [89], [92], [93]
Simulation on Hyperledger Composer/Fabric/Calliper/Ganache/OPENT/Bitcoin/Rinkeyby/AWS/Others	[10], [18], [19], [20], [21], [25], [26], [34], [36], [39], [55], [56], [57], [63], [70], [81], [83], [90], [94], [95], [97]
Performance metrics (latency/throughput/communication cost/computation cost/transaction time/data size/gas spent, etc., depending on proposed models) evaluation by experimentation on various tools	[3], [10], [16], [18], [19], [20], [21], [26], [27], [29], [30], [31], [33], [35], [36], [39], [40], [42], [43], [44], [46], [47], [51], [52], [54], [55], [56], [58], [59], [60], [61], [62], [63], [65], [67], [69], [70], [71], [76], [78], [79], [80], [81], [85], [86], [88], [90], [91], [95], [96], [98]
Theorem-based proof of system security features	[22], [50], [59], [90]
Survey-based system evaluation	[27], [60], [97]

Figure 9.11 Comparison of system evaluation methods used in recent works.

Table 9.6 Common drawbacks found in recent works

Common drawbacks identified	References
Data privacy issue	[9], [10], [18], [22], [27], [40], [47], [51], [60], [66], [68], [72], [76], [78], [79], [87], [88], [89], [92], [93], [95]
Scalability problem	[2], [3], [21], [26], [31], [36], [37], [42], [50], [52], [55], [57], [62], [65], [68], [69], [72], [76], [79], [80], [83], [86], [87], [88], [92]
No standard performance metrics have been evaluated	[2], [23], [24], [28], [37], [38], [48], [57], [68], [75], [82], [83], [84], [89], [92], [93], [94], [97]
Storage and access control is not fully decentralized	[20], [24], [27], [43], [46], [61], [65], [75], [96]
High costs of computation	[2], [33], [60], [81], [92]
No user authentication method	[19], [29], [30], [39]
Decentralized consensus has not been built	[39], [42], [43], [46], [59], [67], [71], [73]
No smart contracts built	[9], [16], [20], [22], [23], [24], [26], [28], [29], [32], [36], [39], [42], [44], [52], [54], [58], [59], [61], [62], [66], [70], [71], [73], [77], [82], [85], [87], [89], [90], [93], [98]

review. In the next section, we have mentioned a detailed set of challenges and future scope which have been identified during this survey.

9.7 Challenges and Future Scope

Besides the potential benefits of blockchain technology to the healthcare industry, significant challenges still exist. We have already discussed the common drawbacks in the previous research works. Some important challenges identified during this review have been summarized below along with some existing systems which have addressed those challenges.

9.7.1 Lack of standardization

The implementation of blockchain-based healthcare systems still lacks in standardization as existing solutions are using different storage methods, consensus algorithms, encryption techniques, and different networks. Consequently, the comparison between these implementations becomes difficult. So there is a need for the evolution of some standards that can help in comparing different solutions. Some systems like [30] and [71] have used standard existing datasets for evaluating and comparing their systems in order to address this problem.

9.7.2 Scalability

As the number of blocks in the application increases, the system becomes computationally slower, and it requires more computational resources and this situation may be worse in an IoT environment where the sensor devices are equipped with limited computational power just enough for performing transmission and receiving data. However, some recent systems [18], [35], [51], have successfully addressed the scalability problem in their models.

9.7.3 Latency

Latency plays an important role in the healthcare sector wherein the personal satisfaction of patients profoundly relies upon continuous medical care frameworks, particularly when healthcare data is gathered through the IoT gadgets and should be recorded into blockchain frameworks. The issue becomes critical when the EHRs are re-evaluated on the brought together distributed storage frameworks. This is because the cloud services may not be accessible at the area of the medical services suppliers, bringing about impressive network latency to re-evaluate the data. It is worth taking note of that network latency has a perceptible effect on fostering a versatile blockchain-based framework. On the other hand, some systems like [31] and [35] have made a successful attempt to address this problem.

9.7.4 Privacy of outsourced data

Data storage is a crucial issue in the blockchain technology that can be handled either on-chain or off-chain. Possible solution followed by existing work is to outsource the healthcare data on the cloud and management of this into the cloud. However, storing and sharing data on cloud computing is

neither secure nor trustable. Moreover, the cloud service providers may be curious about the medical information and overstep the patients' privacy by revealing the healthcare records and other private information. This curious nature of the service providers put the data at risk. However, systems like [28] and [52] have addressed the privacy problem in their models.

Conclusion

In this book chapter, we have provided an exhaustive review of 90 quality articles selected by the SR approach. This review has led to some important findings based on our review questions. There is an enormous future scope of new platforms, consensus methods, and programming languages in the healthcare systems enabled by blockchain technology. We see that a huge proportion of the research works are focused on a limited type of platforms. We can also see that the existing systems have some common drawbacks which need to be addressed in the future works. The findings of this book chapter contribute towards a path for new research works in this domain. We can conclude here by saying that a huge future scope of the blockchain technology can be seen in healthcare applications.

References

- [1] A. Kumar, R. Krishnamurthi, A. Nayyar, K. Sharma, V. Grover, E. Hossain, 'A novel smart healthcare design, simulation, and implementation using healthcare 4.0 processes', *IEEE Access*, 8, 118433-118471, 2020
- [2] J. Vora, A. Nayyar, S. Tanwar, S. Tyagi, N. Kumar, M.S Obaidat, J.J Rodrigues, 'BHEEM: A blockchain-based framework for securing electronic health records', In *2018 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps)*, pp. 1-6, IEEE, Dec., 2018.
- [3] H. Guo, W. Li, E. Meamari, C. Shen, M. Nejad. 'Attribute-based multi-signature and encryption for ehr management: A blockchain-based solution', In *2020 IEEE International Conference on Blockchain and Cryptocurrency (ICBC)*, pp. 1-5, IEEE, May, 2020.
- [4] S. Cao, J. Wang, X. Du, X. Zhang, X. Qin, 'CEPS: A Cross-Blockchain based Electronic Health Records Privacy-Preserving Scheme', In *ICC 2020-2020 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*, pp. 1-6, IEEE, June, 2020.

- 234 *Blockchain in Healthcare: A Systematic Review and Future Perspectives*
- [5] C. Priya, 'Enabling the efficiency of Blockchain Technology in Tele-Healthcare with Enhanced EMR', In 2020 International Conference on Computer Science, Engineering and Applications (ICCSEA), pp. 1-6, IEEE, March 2020.
 - [6] A.I. El Sayed, M. Abdelaziz, M.H. Megahed, M.H.A. Azeem, 'A New Supervision Strategy based on Blockchain for Electronic Health Records', In 2020 12th International Conference on Electrical Engineering (ICEENG), pp. 151-156, IEEE, July 2020.
 - [7] A. Fernandes, V. Rocha, A.F da Conceição, F. Horita, 'Scalable Architecture for sharing EHR using the Hyperledger Blockchain', In 2020 IEEE International Conference on Software Architecture Companion (ICSA-C), pp. 130-138, IEEE, March 2020.
 - [8] Y. Wehbe, M. Al Zaabi, D. Svetinovic, 'Blockchain AI framework for healthcare records management: Constrained goal model', In 2018 26th Telecommunications Forum (TELFOR) pp. 420-425, IEEE, Nov. 2018.
 - [9] R. Guo, H. Shi, Q. Zhao, D. Zheng, 'Secure attribute-based signature scheme with multiple authorities for blockchain in electronic health records systems'. IEEE access, 6, 11676-11686, 2018.
 - [10] V. Jaiman, V. Urovi, 'A consent model for blockchain-based health data sharing platforms', IEEE Access, 8, 143734-143745, 2020.
 - [11] X. Yang, T. Li, W. A. Chen, C. Wang, 'A blockchain-assisted verifiable outsourced attribute-based signcryption scheme for EHRs sharing in the cloud', IEEE Access, 8, 170713-170731, 2020.
 - [12] M. Zarour, M. T.J Ansari, M. Alenezi, A.K Sarkar, M. Faizan, M. A. Agrawal, R. A. Khan, 'Evaluating the impact of blockchain models for secure and trustworthy electronic healthcare records', IEEE Access, 8, 157959-157973, 2020.
 - [13] Y. Zhuang, L. R. Sheets, Y.W Chen, Z. Y. Shae, J.J Tsai, C.R Shyu, 'A patient-centric health information exchange framework using blockchain technology' . IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics, 24(8), 2169-2176, 2020.
 - [14] B. Sharma, R. Halder, J. Singh, 'Blockchain-based interoperable healthcare using zero-knowledge proofs and proxy re-encryption', In 2020 International Conference on Communication Systems & Networks (COMSNETS) (pp. 1-6). IEEE, Jan. 2020.

- [15] A.S Chouhan, M.S Qaseem, Q.M.A Basheer, M.A Mehdiya, 'Blockchain based EHR system architecture and the need of blockchain in healthcare' *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 2021.
- [16] S. Badr, I. Gomaa, E. Abd-Elrahman, 'Multi-tier blockchain framework for IoT-EHRs systems', *Procedia Computer Science*, 141, 159-166, 2018.
- [17] M. Shuaib, S. Alam, M. S Alam, M.S Nasir, 'Compliance with HIPAA and GDPR in blockchain-based electronic health record', *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 2021.
- [18] H. Guo, Li, W., Nejad, C.C Shen, 'Access control for electronic health records with hybrid blockchain-edge architecture', In *2019 IEEE International Conference on Blockchain (Blockchain)* pp. 44-51, IEEE, July 2019.
- [19] D. C Nguyen, P. N. Pathirana, M. Ding, A. Seneviratne, 'Blockchain for secure ehcs sharing of mobile cloud based e-health systems' *IEEE access*, 7, 66792-66806, 2019.
- [20] S. Jiang, H. Wu, L. Wang, 'Patients-controlled secure and privacy-preserving EHRs sharing scheme based on consortium blockchain' In *2019 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM)* (pp. 1-6) IEEE, December 2019.
- [21] Y. Wang, A. Zhang, P. Zhang, H. Wang, 'Cloud-assisted EHR sharing with security and privacy preservation via consortium blockchain', *IEEE Access*, 7, 136704-136719, 2019.
- [22] F. Tang, S. Ma, Y. Xiang, C. Lin, 'An efficient authentication scheme for blockchain-based electronic health records', *IEEE access*, 7, 41678-41689, 2019.
- [23] Y. Wang, M. He, 'CPDS: A Cross-Blockchain Based Privacy-Preserving Data Sharing for Electronic Health Records', In *2021 IEEE 6th International Conference on Cloud Computing and Big Data Analytics (ICCCBDA)*, pp. 90-99 IEEE, April 2021.
- [24] L. Castaldo, V. Cinque, 'Blockchain-based logging for the cross-border exchange of eHealth data in Europe', In *International ISCIS Security Workshop*, pp. 46-56, Springer, Cham, February 2018.
- [25] O. Ajayi, M. Abouali, T. Saadawi, 'Blockchain Architecture for Secured Inter-healthcare Electronic Health Records Exchange', In *International*

- 236 *Blockchain in Healthcare: A Systematic Review and Future Perspectives*
Conference on Intelligent Networking and Collaborative Systems, pp. 161-172, Springer, Cham, August 2020.
- [26] S. M. Pournaghi, M. Bayat, Y. Farjami, 'MedSBA: a novel and secure scheme to share medical data based on blockchain technology and attribute-based encryption', *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, 1-29, 2020.
- [27] P. Meier, J. H. Beinke, C. Fitte, F. Teuteberg, 'Generating design knowledge for blockchain-based access control to personal health records', *Information Systems and e-Business Management*, 19(1), 13-41, 2021.
- [28] A. Al Omar, M. S. Rahman, A. Basu, S. Kiyomoto, 'Medibchain: A blockchain based privacy preserving platform for healthcare data', In *International conference on security, privacy and anonymity in computation, communication and storage*, pp. 534-543, Springer, Cham, December 2017.
- [29] G. Nagasubramanian, R. K. Sakthivel, R. Patan, A. H. Gandomi, M. Sankayya, & B. Balusamy, 'Securing e-health records using keyless signature infrastructure blockchain technology in the cloud', *Neural Computing and Applications*, 32(3), 639-647, 2020.
- [30] N. Sammeta, L. Parthiban, 'Hyperledger blockchain enabled secure medical record management with deep learning-based diagnosis model', *Complex & Intelligent Systems*, 1-16, 2021.
- [31] U. Chelladurai, S. Pandian, 'A novel blockchain based electronic health record automation system for healthcare', *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, 1-11, 2021.
- [32] H. Wang, Y. Song, 'Secure cloud-based EHR system using attribute-based cryptosystem and blockchain', *Journal of medical systems*, 42(8), 1-9, 2018.
- [33] A. Al Omar, M. Z. A. Bhuiyan, A. Basu, S. Kiyomoto, M. S. Rahman, 'Privacy-friendly platform for healthcare data in cloud based on blockchain environment', *Future generation computer systems*, 95, 511-521, 2019.
- [34] M. Antwi, A. Adnane, F. Ahmad, R. Hussain, M. H. ur Rehman, C. A. Kerrache, 'The Case of HyperLedger Fabric as a Blockchain Solution for Healthcare Applications', *Blockchain: Research and Applications*, 100012, March 2021.

- [35] K. Shuaib, J. Abdella, F. Sallabi, M. A. Serhani, 'Secure decentralized electronic health records sharing system based on blockchains', *Journal of King Saud University-Computer and Information Sciences*, 2021.
- [36] T. Benil, J. J. C. N. Jasper, 'Cloud based security on outsourcing using blockchain in E-health systems', *Computer Networks* 178 (2020): 107344, 2020.
- [37] A. Azaria, A. Ekblaw, T. Vieira, A. Lippman, 'Medrec: Using blockchain for medical data access and permission management', In 2016 2nd international conference on open and big data (OBD), pp. 25-30, IEEE, August 2016.
- [38] J. Liu, X. Li, L. Ye, H. Zhang, X. Du, M. Guizani, 'BPDS: A blockchain based privacy-preserving data sharing for electronic medical records', In 2018 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM), pp. 1-6, IEEE, December 2018.
- [39] X. Zhang, S. Poslad, 'Blockchain support for flexible queries with granular access control to electronic medical records (EMR)', In 2018 IEEE International conference on communications (ICC), pp. 1-6 IEEE, May 2018.
- [40] A. Donawa, I. Orukari, C. E. Baker, 'Scaling blockchains to support electronic health records for hospital systems', In 2019 IEEE 10th Annual Ubiquitous Computing, Electronics & Mobile Communication Conference (UEMCON), pp. 0550-0556, IEEE, October 2019.
- [41] Z. Xiao, Z. Li, Y. Liu, L. Feng, W. Zhang, T. Lertwuthikarn, R. S. M. Goh, 'Emrshare: A cross-organizational medical data sharing and management framework using permissioned blockchain', In 2018 IEEE 24th International Conference on Parallel and Distributed Systems (ICPADS), pp. 998-1003, IEEE, December 2018.
- [42] Q. Su, R. Zhang, R. Xue, P. Li, 'Revocable attribute-based signature for blockchain-based healthcare system', *IEEE Access*, 8, 127884-127896, 2020.
- [43] B. Toshniwal, P. Podili, R. J. Reddy, K. Kataoka, 'PACEX: PATient-Centric EMR eXchange in Healthcare Systems using Blockchain', In 2019 IEEE 10th Annual Information Technology, Electronics and Mobile Communication Conference (IEMCON), pp. 0954-0960, IEEE, October 2019.

238 *Blockchain in Healthcare: A Systematic Review and Future Perspectives*

- [44] D. C. Nguyen, P. N. Pathirana, M. Ding, A. Seneviratne, 'Blockchain and edge computing for decentralized EMRs sharing in federated healthcare', In GLOBECOM 2020-2020 IEEE Global Communications Conference, pp. 1-6, IEEE, December 2020.
- [45] W. Jiamsawat, C. Choksuchat, S. Matayong, 'Blockchain-Based Electronic Medical Records Management of Hospital Emergency Ward', In 2021 International Conference on COMMunication Systems & NETWORKS (COMSNETS), pp. 674-679, IEEE, January 2021.
- [46] S. Biswas, K. Sharif, F. Li, I. Alam, S. Mohanty, 'DAAC: Digital Asset Access Control in a Unified Blockchain Based E-Health System', IEEE Transactions on Big Data, 2020.
- [47] A. Martínez, C. Molina, D. Subauste, 'Electronic Medical Records Management in Health Organizations using a Technology Architecture based on Blockchain', In 2020 IEEE ANDESCON, pp. 1-6, IEEE, October 2020.
- [48] A. Dubovitskaya, Z. Xu, S. Ryu, M. Schumacher, F. Wang, 'Secure and trustable electronic medical records sharing using blockchain', In AMIA annual symposium proceedings, Vol. 2017, p. 650, American Medical Informatics Association, 2017.
- [49] G. Wu, S. Wang, Z. Ning, B. Zhu, 'Privacy-Preserved EMR Information Publishing and Sharing: A Blockchain-Enabled Smart Healthcare System', IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics, 2021.
- [50] Y. S. Lo, C. Y. Yang, H. F. Chien, S. S. Chang, C. Y. Lu, R. J. Chen, 'Blockchain-enabled iWellChain framework integration with the national medical referral system: development and usability study', Journal of medical Internet research, 21(12), e13563, 2019.
- [51] A. Shahnaz, U. Qamar, A. Khalid, 'Using blockchain for electronic health records', IEEE Access, 7, 147782-147795, 2019.
- [52] X. Liu, Z. Wang, C. Jin, F. Li, G. Li, 'A blockchain-based medical data sharing and protection scheme', IEEE Access, 7, 118943-118953, 2019.
- [53] S. Shamshad, K. Mahmood, S. Kumari, C. M. Chen, 'Cloud-assisted secure eHealth systems for tamper-proofing EHR via blockchain', Journal of Information Security and Applications, 55, 102590, 2020.
- [54] S. Cao, G. Zhang, P. Liu, X. Zhang, F. Neri, 'Cloud-assisted secure eHealth systems for tamper-proofing EHR via blockchain', Information Sciences, 485, 427-440, 2019.

- [55] L. Chen, W. K. Lee, C. C. Chang, K. K. R. Choo, N. Zhang, 'Blockchain based searchable encryption for electronic health record sharing', *Future generation computer systems*, 95, 420-429, 2019.
- [56] S. Tanwar, K. Parekh, R. Evans, 'Blockchain-based electronic healthcare record system for healthcare 4.0 applications', *Journal of Information Security and Applications*, 50, 102407, 2020.
- [57] S. S. R. Krishnan, M. K. Manoj, T. R. Gadekallu, N. Kumar, P. K. R. Maddikunta, S. Bhattacharya, M. J. Piran, 'A Blockchain-Based Credibility Scoring Framework for Electronic Medical Records', In *2020 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps)*, pp. 1-6, IEEE, December 2020.
- [58] K. Fan, S. Wang, Y. Ren, H. Li, Y. Yang, 'Medblock: Efficient and secure medical data sharing via blockchain', *Journal of medical systems*, 42(8), 1-11, 2018.
- [59] J. Fu, N. Wang, Y. Cai, 'Privacy-preserving in healthcare blockchain systems based on lightweight message sharing. *Sensors*', 20 (7), 1898, 2020.
- [60] O. Gutiérrez, G. Romero, L. Pérez, A. Salazar, M. Charris, P. Wightman, 'Healthy Block: Blockchain-Based IT Architecture for Electronic Medical Records Resilient to Connectivity Failures', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(19), 7132, 2020.
- [61] H. Zhu, Y. Guo, L. Zhang, 'An improved convolution Merkle tree-based blockchain electronic medical record secure storage scheme', *Journal of Information Security and Applications*, 61, 102952, 2021.
- [62] R. Johari, V. Kumar, K. Gupta, D. P. Vidyarthi, 'BLOSOM: BLockchain technology for Security of Medical records', *ICT Express*, 2021.
- [63] R. Zou, X. Lv, J. Zhao, 'SPChain: Blockchain-based medical data sharing and privacy-preserving eHealth system', *Information Processing & Management*, 58(4), 102604, 2021.
- [64] M. Usman, U. Qamar, 'Secure electronic medical records storage and sharing using blockchain technology', *Procedia Computer Science*, 174, 321-327, 2020.
- [65] Z. Chen, W. Xu, B. Wang, H. Yu, 'A blockchain-based preserving and sharing system for medical data privacy', *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 2021.

- 240 *Blockchain in Healthcare: A Systematic Review and Future Perspectives*
- [66] G. Tripathi, M. A. Ahad, S. Paiva, 'S2HS-A blockchain based approach for smart healthcare system. In *Healthcare*', Vol. 8, No. 1, p. 100391, Elsevier, March 2020.
- [67] C. Zhang, C. Xu, K. Sharif, L. Zhu, 'Privacy-preserving contact tracing in 5G-integrated and blockchain-based medical applications', *Computer Standards & Interfaces*, 77, 103520, 2021.
- [68] R. M. A. Latif, K. Hussain, N. Z. Jhanjhi, A. Nayyar, O. Rizwan, 'A remix IDE: smart contract-based framework for the healthcare sector by using Blockchain technology', *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 1-24, 2020.
- [69] M. Sultana, A. Hossain, F. Laila, K. A. Taher, M. N. Islam, 'Towards developing a secure medical image sharing system based on zero trust principles and blockchain technology', *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, 20(1), 1-10, 2020.
- [70] T. Zhou, X. Li, H. Zhao, 'Med-PPPHIS: blockchain-based personal healthcare information system for national physique monitoring and scientific exercise guiding', *Journal of medical systems*, 43(9), 1-23, 2019.
- [71] A. Mubarakali, 'Healthcare services monitoring in cloud using secure and robust healthcare-based BLOCKCHAIN (SRHB) approach', *Mobile Networks and Applications*, 25(4), 1330-1337, 2020.
- [72] T. Bocek, B. B. Rodrigues, T. Strasser, B. Stiller, 'Blockchains everywhere-a use-case of blockchains in the pharma supply-chain', In *2017 IFIP/IEEE symposium on integrated network and service management (IM)*, pp. 772-777, IEEE, May 2017.
- [73] R. Kumar, R. Tripathi, 'Traceability of counterfeit medicine supply chain through Blockchain', In *2019 11th International Conference on Communication Systems & Networks (COMSNETS)*, pp. 568-570, IEEE, January 2019.
- [74] V. Ahmadi, S. Benjelloun, M. El Kik, T. Sharma, H. Chi, W. Zhou, 'Drug governance: IoT-based blockchain implementation in the pharmaceutical supply chain', In *2020 Sixth International Conference on Mobile and Secure Services (MobiSecServ)*, pp. 1-8, IEEE, February 2020.

- [75] G. Subramanian, A. S. Thampy, N. V. Ugwuoke, B. Ramnani, 'Crypto Pharmacy–Digital Medicine: A Mobile Application Integrated With Hybrid Blockchain to Tackle the Issues in Pharma Supply Chain', *IEEE Open Journal of the Computer Society*, 2, 26-37, 2021.
- [76] R. W. Ahmad, K. Salah, R. Jayaraman, I. Yaqoob, M. Omar, S. Ellahham, 'Blockchain-Based Forward Supply Chain and Waste Management for COVID-19 Medical Equipment and Supplies', *IEEE Access*, 9, 44905-44927, 2021.
- [77] Y. Yue, X. Fu, 'Research on Medical Equipment Supply Chain Management Method Based on Blockchain Technology', In 2020 International Conference on Service Science (ICSS), pp. 143-148, IEEE, August 2020.
- [78] H. Kumiawan, J. Kim, H. Ju, 'Utilization of the Blockchain Network in The Public Community Health Center Medicine Supply Chain', In 2020 21st Asia-Pacific Network Operations and Management Symposium (APNOMS), pp. 235-238, IEEE, September 2020.
- [79] A. Musamih, K. Salah, R. Jayaraman, J. Arshad, M. Debe, Y. Al-Hammadi, S. Ellahham, 'A Blockchain-Based Approach for Drug Traceability in Healthcare Supply Chain', *IEEE Access*, 9, 9728-9743, 2021
- [80] I. A. Omar, R. Jayaraman, M. S. Debe, K. Salah, I. Yaqoob, M. Omar, 'Automating procurement contracts in the healthcare supply chain using blockchain smart contracts', *IEEE Access*, 9, 37397-37409, 2021.
- [81] S. K. Panda, S. C. Satapathy, 'Drug traceability and transparency in medical supply chain using blockchain for easing the process and creating trust between stakeholders and consumers', *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing*, 1-17, 2021.
- [82] Y. Kong, Y. Wang, "'Blockchain Plus Supply Chain Finance" Boosts Pharmaceutical Industry: A Case Study of Jixiangtian Blockchain Medical and Health Service Platform', In *E3S Web of Conferences*, Vol. 292, EDP Sciences, 2021.
- [83] G. Saldamli, V. Reddy, K. S. Bojja, M. K. Gururaja, Y. Doddaveerappa, L. Tawalbeh, 'Health Care Insurance Fraud Detection Using Blockchain', In 2020 Seventh International Conference on Software Defined Systems (SDS), pp. 145-152, IEEE, April 2020.

242 *Blockchain in Healthcare: A Systematic Review and Future Perspectives*

- [84] W. Liu, Q. Yu, Z. Li, Z. Li, Y. Su, J. Zhou, 'A blockchain-based system for anti-fraud of healthcare insurance', In 2019 IEEE 5th International Conference on Computer and Communications (ICCC), pp. 1264-1268, IEEE, December, 2019.
- [85] B. Alhasan, M. Qatawneh, W. Almobaideen, 'Blockchain Technology for Preventing Counterfeit in Health Insurance', In 2021 International Conference on Information Technology (ICIT), pp. 935-941, IEEE, July 2021.
- [86] M. H. Chinaei, H. H. Gharakheili, & V. Sivaraman, 'Optimal Witnessing of Healthcare IoT Data Using Blockchain Logging Contract', IEEE Internet of Things Journal, 2021.
- [87] M. Thenmozhi, R. Dhanalakshmi, S. Geetha, R. Valli, 'Implementing blockchain technologies for health insurance claim processing in hospitals', Materials Today: Proceedings, 2021.
- [88] A. Goyal, A. Elhence, V. Chamola, B. Sikdar, 'A Blockchain and Machine Learning based Framework for Efficient Health Insurance Management', In Proceedings of the 19th ACM Conference on Embedded Networked Sensor Systems, pp. 511-515, November 2021.
- [89] Y. Huang, J. Wu, & C. Long, 'Drug ledger: A practical blockchain system for drug traceability and regulation', In 2018 IEEE International Conference on Internet of Things (iThings) and IEEE Green Computing and Communications (GreenCom) and IEEE Cyber, Physical and Social Computing (CPSCom) and IEEE Smart Data (SmartData), pp. 1137-1144, IEEE, July 2018.
- [90] W. Xie, B. Wang, Z. Ye, W. Wu, J. You, Q. Zhou, 'Simulation-based blockchain design to secure biopharmaceutical supply chain', In 2019 Winter Simulation Conference (WSC), pp. 797-808, IEEE, December 2019.
- [91] X. Liu, A. V. Barenji, Z. Li, B. Montreuil, G. Q. Huang, 'Blockchain-based smart tracking and tracing platform for drug supply chain', Computers & Industrial Engineering, 161, 107669, 2021.
- [92] M. Uddin, 'Blockchain Medledger: Hyperledger fabric enabled drug traceability system for counterfeit drugs in pharmaceutical industry', International Journal of Pharmaceutics, 597, 120235, 2021.

- [93] J. H. Tseng, Y. C. Liao, B. Chong, S. W. Liao, 'Governance on the drug supply chain via gcoin blockchain', *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 15(6), 1055, 2018.
- [94] P. Sylim, F. Liu, A. Marcelo, P. Fontelo, 'Blockchain technology for detecting falsified and substandard drugs in distribution: pharmaceutical supply chain intervention', *JMIR research protocols*, 7(9), e10163, 2018.
- [95] K. Abbas, M. Afaq, T. Ahmed Khan, W. C. Song, 'A blockchain and machine learning-based drug supply chain management and recommendation system for the smart pharmaceutical industry', *Electronics*, 9(5), 852, 2020.
- [96] E. Ehioghae, S. Idowu, O. Ebiesuwa, 'Enhanced Drug Anti-Counterfeiting and Verification System for the Pharmaceutical Drug Supply Chain using Blockchain', *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 975, 8887, February 2021.
- [97] W. Chien, J. de Jesus, B. Taylor, V. Dods, L. Alekseyev, D. Shoda, P. B. Shieh, 'The last mile: DSCSA solution through blockchain technology: drug tracking, tracing, and verification at the last mile of the pharmaceutical supply chain with BRUINchain', *Blockchain in Healthcare Today*, 2020.
- [98] S. Shamshad, K. Mahmood, S. Kumari, C. M. Chen, 'A secure blockchain-based e-health records storage and sharing scheme', *Journal of Information Security and Applications*, 55, 102590, 2020.

Australian Government

IP Australia

CERTIFICATE OF GRANT INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2021104722

The Commissioner of Patents has granted the above patent on 30 March 2022, and certifies that the below particulars have been registered in the Register of Patents.

Name and address of patentee(s):

Karuna Pandit of Professor, Department of Information Science & Engineering, NMAMIT, Nitte, Karkala Taluk Udipi District Karnataka 574110 India

K. E. Prakash of Principal and Director, Shree Devi Institute of Technology, Kenjar Mangalore 574142 India

Vishal Dattana of Moodle Administrator and Senior Lecturer, Department of Computing, Middle East College, Sultanate of Oman Muscat 124 Oman

Manju Jose of Assistant Professor and Programme Manager, Department of Computing, Middle East College, Sultanate of Oman Muscat 124 Oman

Sonia V. Soans of Lecturer, Information Technology, University of Tech. & Applied Sciences Muscat 611 Oman

Priyanka Sharma of Assistant Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Poomima College of Engineering Jaipur Rajasthan 302022 India

Shwetha Pai of Research Scholar, College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University Mangalore Karnataka 575001 India

Jitendranath Mungara of Principal & Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Nagarjuna College of Engineering & Technology Bangalore Karnataka 562110 India

Muthukumar Subramanian of DEAN & Professor, Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering Nagarjuna College of Engineering & Tech. Bangalore, Karnataka 562110 India

Dinesha H A of Professor & HoD, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Nagarjuna College of Engineering & Technology Bangalore Karnataka 562110 India

Yashwanth N of Associate Professor, Dept. of ECE, Nagarjuna College of Engineering and Technology Bangalore Karnataka 562110 India

S. Deepajothi of Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Nagarjuna College of Engineering and Technology Bengaluru Karnataka 562110 India

Mohammed Azam of Research Scholar, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Shri Jagdishprasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University Jhunjhunu Rajasthan 333001 India

Title of invention:

MACHINE LEARNING AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE BASED INTELLIGENT BETTING SYSTEM FOR SPORTS PREDICTION

Name of inventor(s):

Pandit, Karuna; Prakash, K. E.; Dattana, Vishal; Jose, Manju; Soans, Sonia V.; Sharma, Priyanka; Pai, Shwetha; Mungara, Jitendranath; S., Muthukumar; H. A., Dinesha; N., Yashwanth; Deepajothi, S. and Azam, Mohammed

Dated this 30th day of March 2022

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

The Australian Patents Register is the official record and should be referred to for the full details pertaining to this IP Right.

CERTIFICATE OF GRANT INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2021104977

The Commissioner of Patents has granted the above patent on 13 April 2022, and certifies that the below particulars have been registered in the Register of Patents.

Name and address of patentee(s):

Pankaj Mudholkar of Assistant Professor, Dept. Master of Computer Applications (MCA), Thakur Institute of Management Studies, Career Development & Research Mumbai Maharashtra 400101 India

Megha Mudholkar of Assistant Professor, Dept: Master of Computer Applications (MCA), Thakur Institute of Management Studies, Career Development & Research Mumbai Maharashtra 400101 India

Kusum Yadav of Associate Professor, College of Computer Science and Engineering, University of Ha'il Ha'il 81141 Saudi Arabia

Mannava Yesubabu of Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Vardhaman College of Engineering, Shamshabad Hyderabad 501218 India

Amedapu Srinivas of Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Sreenidhi Institute of Science and Technology Hyderabad 501218 India

Gaurav Indra of Assistant Professor, Department of Information Technology, Indra Gandhi Delhi Technical University For Women, Kashmere Gate New Delhi 110006 India

Vishal Dattana of Moodle Administrator and Senior Lecturer, Department of Computing, Middle East College Muscat 124 Oman

Nethravathi P.S of Professor, College of Computer and Information Science, Srinivas University Mangalore Karnataka 575001 India

Sonia V. Soans of Lecturer, Department of Information Technology, University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Muscat State Muscat 611 Oman

Jyoti Dashora of Assistant Professor, Sangam University Bhillwara Rajasthan 311001 India

Ansuman Samal of Associate Professor, Faculty of Hospitality and Tourism Management, Siksha O Anusandhan Deemed to be University Bhubaneswar Odisha 751030 India

Karunesh Saxena. of Vice Chancellor, Sangam University Bhillwara Rajasthan 31100 India

Ravinder M of Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Indra Gandhi Delhi Technical University for Women, Madrasa Road, Opposite St. James Church, Kashmere Gate Delhi 110006 India

Title of invention:

INTELLIGENT SYSTEM & METHOD TO PROTECT AND SECURE ENVIRONMENT OF PREMISES USING IOT NETWORK

Name of inventor(s):

Dated this 13th day of April 2022

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

The Australian Patents Register is the official record and should be referred to for the full details pertaining to this IP Right.

Australian Government
IP Australia

CERTIFICATE OF GRANT INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2021104977

Mudholkar, Pankaj; Mudholkar, Megha; Yadav, Kusum; Yesubabu, Mannava; Srinivas, Amedapu; Indra, Gaurav; Dattana, Vishal; P. S., Nethravathi; Soans, Sonia V.; Dashora, Jyoti; Samal, Ansuman; Saxena., Karunesh and M., Ravinder

Term of Patent:

Eight years from 5 August 2021

NOTE: This Innovation Patent cannot be enforced unless and until it has been examined by the Commissioner of Patents and a Certificate of Examination has been issued. See sections 120(1A) and 129A of the Patents Act 1990, set out on the reverse of this document.

Dated this 13th day of April 2022

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

The Australian Patents Register is the official record and should be referred to for the full details pertaining to this IP Right.

Conclusion:

This research has allowed researchers to delve deep into the intricate world of wireless networks, addressing critical challenges that are becoming increasingly pertinent in the digital age.

Throughout this postdoctoral study, the pressing need for innovative strategies that balance the ever-growing demand for wireless connectivity with the imperative to maintain security and energy efficiency has been identified. A comprehensive examination of existing technologies, protocols, and methodologies has shed light on the strengths and weaknesses of current solutions, providing valuable insights into potential areas of improvement.

By proposing and developing new strategies, such as optimized encryption protocols, dynamic energy-efficient routing algorithms, and intelligent network management approaches, significant strides have been made towards achieving a more secure and energy-efficient wireless network ecosystem. These advancements not only enhance the overall performance and reliability of wireless networks but also contribute to reducing their environmental impact and operational costs.

The findings and contributions made during this postdoctoral research will undoubtedly have a lasting impact on the field of wireless networking. They open up new avenues for further exploration and innovation, paving the way for a future where wireless networks are not only faster and more reliable but also more secure and environmentally sustainable.

As this postdoctoral journey concludes, it is important to acknowledge the collaborative efforts of fellow researchers, mentors, and institutions that have supported this endeavor. Together, the research community has expanded its understanding of wireless networks, pushing the boundaries of what is possible in the quest for a safer, more energy-efficient, and interconnected world.

In the coming years, the insights gained from this research will continue to inform the development of wireless technologies, fostering a brighter, more sustainable future for all. The pursuit of security and energy efficiency in wireless networks remains a dynamic and evolving field, and as researchers, the commitment to the ongoing pursuit of knowledge and innovation in this critical domain is paramount.